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ABSTRACT

The description of geophysical granular flows, like avalanches and debris flows, is a challenging open problem due to the high complexity of the granular dynamics, which is characterized by various momentum exchange mechanisms and is strongly coupled with the solid volume fraction field. In order to capture the rich variability of the granular dynamics along the avalanche depth, we present a well-posed multilayer model, where various layers, made of the same granular material, are advected in a dynamically coupled way. The stress and shear-rate tensors are related to each other by the $\mu(I)$ rheology. A variable volume fraction field is introduced through a relaxation argument and is governed by a dilatancy law depending on the inertial number, I . To avoid short-wave instabilities, which are a well-known issue of the conditionally hyperbolic multilayer models and also of three-dimensional models implementing the $\mu(I)$ rheology, a physically based viscous regularization using a sensible approximation of the in-plane stress gradients is proposed. Linear stability analyses in the short-wave limit show the suitability of the proposed regularization in ensuring the model well-posedness and also in providing a finite cutoff frequency for the short-wave instabilities, which is beneficial for the practical convergence of numerical simulations. The model is numerically integrated by a time-splitting finite volume scheme with a high-resolution lateralized Harten–Lax–van Leer (LHLL) solver. Numerical tests illustrate the main features and the robust numerical stability of the model.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Granular media are ubiquitously involved in industrial applications and natural phenomena, like debris flows and avalanches (e.g., Savage, 1984; Iverson, 1997; Ancey, 2001; Goldhirsch, 2003). The development of mathematical–numerical tools, capable of describing the motion of granular materials, is of utmost importance, especially in the context of risk assessment of natural disasters. Increasing attention to geophysical flows has stimulated several experimental and theoretical studies focusing on the dynamics of granular media and liquid–granular mixtures (GDR MiDi, 2004; Jop *et al.*, 2005; Pudasaini *et al.*, 2007; Gray and Ancey, 2009; Sarno *et al.*, 2011; Sarno *et al.*, 2018a, 2018b; Sarno *et al.*, 2019; Meng and Wang, 2016; Heß *et al.*, 2017; Meninno *et al.*, 2018; Amicarelli *et al.*, 2020). While the granular materials are composed of a large number of solid particles, a convenient theoretical approach consists of regarding them as a *continuum*. In this framework, a major open problem concerns an universal

rheology capable of describing the broad variety of flow regimes (e.g., Wang and Hutter, 2001; Jop, 2015; Guo *et al.*, 2021). This difficulty is magnified by the lack of a neat separation between microscopic and macroscopic time scales (Goldhirsch, 2003; GDR MiDi, 2004), often causing significant non-local interactions between the stress and the shear-rate tensors (e.g., Aranson and Tsimring, 2002; Kamrin, 2019; Lin and Yang, 2021). With reference to the intermediate dense-collisional regime, emerging most frequently in nature, a well-established viscoplastic rheology is the $\mu(I)$ theory (Pouliquen and Forterre, 2002; Jop *et al.*, 2005; Jop *et al.*, 2006), where a Coulomb-like friction is postulated to depend on the inertial number, I (Savage, 1984; Ancey *et al.*, 1999). Despite its phenomenological approach, the $\mu(I)$ rheology has gained increasing experimental support (e.g., GDR MiDi, 2004; Jop *et al.*, 2005; Forterre, 2006; Gray and Edwards, 2014). The $\mu(I)$ rheology has been incorporated into a three-dimensional (3D) Navier–Stokes model by Lagrée *et al.* (2011), subsequently validated by Staron *et al.* (2014) against discrete contact dynamics

simulations. [Barker et al. \(2015\)](#) showed that, different from a rate-independent friction law ([Schaeffer, 1987](#)), the $\mu(I)$ rheology exhibits an intermediate interval of I (spanning around two orders of magnitude), where the corresponding incompressible 3D model is well-posed, while outside of this interval, a non-trivial model regularization is required.

A limitation of three-dimensional models is the high computational cost, especially relevant for large domains. Hence, even with today's availability of relatively complete rheological theories, the necessity of efficient models justifies the employment of a depth-averaged approach (e.g., [Grigorian et al., 1967](#); [Savage and Hutter, 1989](#); [Gray et al., 1999](#); [Hutter et al., 2005](#); [Tai and Kuo, 2008](#); [Papa et al., 2018](#)). Akin to the shallow water equations of hydraulics ([de Saint-Venant, 1871](#)), the depth-averaged models are typically of hyperbolic type and admit a straightforward numerical integration. With this approach, the capability of 3D models of capturing the full dynamics is traded off for a simpler lower-dimensional model. While this compromise is acceptable in the case of blunt velocity profiles, typical of avalanches on a smooth bed (e.g., [Savage and Hutter, 1989](#); [Gray et al., 1999](#)), it may become inadequate if the velocity profiles are highly sheared or rapidly change in shape (e.g., [Silbert et al., 2003](#); [Jop et al., 2005](#); [Lanzoni et al., 2017](#)). This rich variety of velocity profiles is often associated with an uneven topography and also with the presence of a narrow cross section, which promotes the onset of a rheological stratification ([Armanini et al. 2005](#); [Jop et al., 2005](#); [Sarno et al., 2018b](#)). Moreover, the complex interplay between the collisional and frictional momentum exchange mechanisms is strongly coupled with the solid volume fraction ([Bagnold, 1954](#); [Savage, 1979](#); [Josserand et al., 2004](#); [Sarno et al., 2016](#); [Sarno et al., 2020](#)).

To better capture the dynamics of stratified flows, a natural extension of the classical depth-averaged models is represented by two- and multi-layer models (e.g., [Audusse, 2005](#); [Doyle et al., 2011](#); [Sarno et al., 2014](#); [Fernández-Nieto et al., 2016](#); [Meng et al., 2017](#)). To describe free surface flows of Newtonian fluids in a computationally more efficient way than the 3D Navier–Stokes equations, a multilayer Saint–Venant model with immiscible layers was introduced by [Audusse \(2005\)](#) and numerically investigated by [Audusse and Bristeau \(2007\)](#). An alternative model with mass exchanges was proposed by [Audusse et al. \(2011a\)](#) and extended by [Audusse et al. \(2011b\)](#) to Newtonian fluids with variable density. A similar multilayer model, derived by using piecewise smooth weak solutions, was proposed by [Fernández-Nieto et al. \(2014\)](#) for Newtonian flows and by [Fernández-Nieto et al. \(2016, 2018\)](#) for dense granular flows.

A well-known issue of multilayer models, also in common with two-layer ([Long, 1956](#); [Greco et al., 2008](#); [Abgrall and Karni, 2009](#)) and two-phase models ([Keyfitz et al., 2003](#); [Pelanti et al., 2008](#)), is the possible loss of hyperbolicity, which leads to Hadamard ill-posedness, i.e., unbounded growth rates of short-wave instabilities ([Joseph and Saut, 1990](#)). Namely, the propagation speeds of the infinitesimal perturbations at the layers' interfaces may become complex under certain flow conditions. While this occurrence is partially due to the model oversimplification, it is often associated with real physical phenomena, namely, Kelvin–Helmholtz instabilities of the layers' interfaces and also Rayleigh–Taylor instabilities, if the layers' densities are not monotonically increasing along the flow thickness. In the simple context of two-layer models, several approaches have been proposed for the model regularization, e.g., the introduction of turbulent-like

momentum exchanges between the layers ([Castro et al., 2011](#); [Sarno et al., 2017](#); [Krvavica et al., 2018](#); [Sarno et al., 2021b](#)), the introduction of some artificial viscosity ([Holmås et al., 2008](#); [Etrati and Frigaard, 2018](#)), or the implementation of a finite relaxation time for the pressure coupling between the layers ([Abgrall and Karni, 2009](#); [Chiapolino and Saurel, 2018](#)). In the context of multilayer models, the hyperbolicity loss has been numerically circumvented by [Audusse \(2005\)](#) by treating the non-conservative terms as external source terms. More recently, [Audusse et al. \(2011a\)](#) proposed to enforce that the layers form a preset partition of the total depth, so as to inhibit interface instabilities. This approach, also adopted by [Fernández-Nieto et al. \(2014, 2016\)](#), represents a significant improvement for the numerical stability. Yet, while [Audusse et al. \(2011a\)](#) proved the strict hyperbolicity for the special case of two layers, even with this approach the multilayer model may still lose its hyperbolic character in cases with more than two layers ([Audusse et al., 2014](#)).

Inspired by the aforementioned works, in this paper we present a well-posed multilayer model, obtained by a physically based regularization. The model, implementing the $\mu(I)$ rheology, uses a parsimonious number of parameters and has low computational costs, compared to 3D models. Its mathematical formulation is given in a general form, allowing a secondary volume fraction variation within the layers. To ensure the well-posedness of the model for any value of the inertial number, a suitable approximation of the in-plane stress gradients is introduced in the momentum equations. Although the in-plane deviatoric stresses are typically neglected in first-order depth-averaged models, it is worth mentioning that they were found to play a crucial role in capturing the roll waves of dry granular flows ([Forterre, 2006](#); [Gray and Edwards, 2014](#)). In the multilayer approach, the number of the layers can be arbitrarily chosen and the layers' evolution is fully governed by the selected rheology. Hence, for a sufficiently high number of layers, the proposed multilayer model can be regarded as a computationally efficient tool to approximate and regularize the corresponding 3D model with the $\mu(I)$ rheology.

The outline of the paper is as follows. In [Sec. II](#), the governing equations and the constitutive laws are briefly described. In [Sec. III](#), the model equations are derived by asymptotic approximation and are equipped with suitable closures. In [Sec. IV](#), linear stability analyses in the short-wave limit are carried out to investigate the model well-posedness. Some numerical tests are presented in [Sec. V](#). Finally, the discussion and conclusion are summarized in [Sec. VI](#).

II. GOVERNING EQUATIONS AND CONSTITUTIVE LAWS

Adopting the tension-positive convention, the balance equations for mass and linear momentum are

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t \rho + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0, \\ \partial_t (\rho \mathbf{u}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T} = \rho \mathbf{g}, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\nabla \cdot$ and \otimes stand for the divergence and the dyadic product, respectively. In [Eq. \(1\)](#), $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the velocity field, $\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the Cauchy total stress tensor, \mathbf{g} represents the gravity vector, and $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = \rho_g \nu(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the bulk density, where ρ_g stands for the grain true density and $\nu(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the solid volume fraction. As the confining pressure is typically small in geophysical flows (e.g., [Savage, 1984](#)), the

grains can be treated as incompressible, $\rho_g = \text{const}$. Hence, Eq. (1) is recast as

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t \nu + \nabla \cdot (\nu \mathbf{u}) = 0, \\ \partial_t (\nu \mathbf{u}) + \nabla \cdot (\nu \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) - \frac{\nabla \cdot \mathbf{T}}{\rho_g} = \nu \mathbf{g}. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Let Oxz be an orthonormal Cartesian coordinate system, with x axis parallel to the downward slope, rotated by an angle ζ to the horizontal, and the z axis pointing upward perpendicularly to the slope. Decomposing the stress tensor into $\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{x}, t) = -p(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{T}^*(\mathbf{x}, t)$, with p being the isotropic pressure and $\mathbf{1}$ the identity matrix, Eq. (2) yields the following scalar equations for two-dimensional granular flows,

$$\partial_t \nu + \partial_x (\nu u_x) + \partial_z (\nu u_z) = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t (\nu u_x) + \partial_x (\nu u_x^2) + \partial_z (\nu u_x u_z) + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (\partial_x p - \partial_x t_{xx}^* - \partial_z t_{xz}^*) \\ = \nu g \sin \zeta, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t (\nu u_z) + \partial_x (\nu u_x u_z) + \partial_z (\nu u_z^2) + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (\partial_z p - \partial_x t_{xz}^* - \partial_z t_{zz}^*) \\ = -\nu g \cos \zeta \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where t_{ij}^* is the ij component of \mathbf{T}^* . As the variation of ν is typically small in the dense regime (e.g., GDR MiDi, 2004; Sheng et al., 2011; Meninno et al., 2018; Carleo et al., 2019; Bhateja and Khakhar, 2020; Sarno et al., 2021a), the impact of the compressibility on the pressure, p , and on the stress tensor, \mathbf{T}^* , is assumed to be negligible.

A. $\mu(I)$ rheology

The $\mu(I)$ rheology, developed for dense granular flows by Jop et al. (2005, 2006), is here employed. It postulates that \mathbf{T}^* is related to the strain-rate tensor, $\mathbf{D} = 1/2(\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T)$, by the viscoplastic relationship,

$$\mathbf{T}^* = 2\eta(I, p)\mathbf{D} = \frac{\sqrt{2}\mu(I)p}{\|\mathbf{D}\|}\mathbf{D}. \quad (6)$$

Here, $\|\mathbf{D}\| = \sqrt{\mathbf{D} : \mathbf{D}}$ is the Frobenius tensor norm (e.g., Goddard, 1986; Wang and Hutter, 2001), while η is a viscosity function, depending on both p and the inertial number, I , which is the square root of the Savage number (Savage, 1984; Ancy et al., 1999),

$$I = \frac{\sqrt{2}d_g \|\mathbf{D}\|}{\sqrt{p/\rho_g}}, \quad (7)$$

with d_g being the characteristic grain diameter. The inertial number is usually defined for the incompressible case, i.e., $\rho = \rho_g \nu = \text{const}$ (Jop et al., 2006). An extension to granular flows with variable volume fraction was proposed by Börzsönyi et al. (2009), where $\|\mathbf{D}\|$ was substituted by the norm of the traceless part of the strain-rate tensor, \mathbf{D} . Considering that the volume fraction variations are typically small and also in view of the subsequent leading-order approximations of \mathbf{D} (see Sec. III D), in (7) we kept \mathbf{D} unmodified. From experiments, Jop et al. (2005) found that the apparent friction, $\mu(I)$, can be described as

$$\mu(I) = \mu_s + \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_s}{I_0/I + 1}. \quad (8)$$

Here, μ_s is the friction coefficient at zero shear rate, μ_2 is the saturation value of the friction coefficient, and I_0 is a constant parameter. Together with (8), it is clear that Eq. (6) incorporates a yield stress, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{T}^* = \sqrt{2}\mu_s p \frac{\mathbf{D}}{\|\mathbf{D}\|} + 2\tilde{\eta}\mathbf{D} = \sqrt{2}\mu_s p \hat{\mathbf{D}} + 2\tilde{\eta}\mathbf{D}, \quad (9)$$

where $\sqrt{2}\mu_s p$ is the plastic modulus and $\tilde{\eta}$ is a rate-dependent viscosity that reads as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\eta}(p, I, \|\mathbf{D}\|) &= \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_s)p}{\sqrt{2}(I_0/I + 1)\|\mathbf{D}\|} \\ &= \frac{d_g(\mu_2 - \mu_s)\sqrt{\rho_g}}{\left(I_0 + \sqrt{2}d_g\|\mathbf{D}\|/\sqrt{p/\rho_g}\right)}\sqrt{p}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

For $I \ll I_0$, a first-order approximation of (8) is $\mu(I) = \mu_s + [(\mu_2 - \mu_s)/I_0] \cdot I$, so that (10) is simplified into $\tilde{\eta} \approx [d_g(\mu_2 - \mu_s)\sqrt{\rho_g}/I_0]\sqrt{p}$.

B. Dilatancy

The dilatancy phenomenon (Reynolds, 1885) can be described by an equation of state (EOS) relating the volume fraction field and the granular dynamics. While non-local effects, mediated by some order-parameter (e.g., the volume fraction) describing the transition between solid and fluidized states, are relevant in the quasi-static and dense regimes (e.g., Aranson and Tsimring, 2002; Kamrin, 2019), for dilute flows the relationship between the volume fraction and the rate of deformation becomes weaker and the grain velocity fluctuations are expected to play a significant role (Savage, 1984). Da Cruz et al. (2005) suggested to describe the dilatancy of steady 2D shear flows in the slow regime ($I < 0.20$) by

$$\nu(I) = \nu_{\max} - aI, \quad (11)$$

where ν represents the average volume fraction, ν_{\max} is the maximum packing fraction, and a is an empirical parameter. By numerically investigating chute flows, Börzsönyi et al. (2009) found that a monotonically decreasing relationship, like Eq. (11), is also valid in a local sense and for a wider range of ν . Experimental support of a dilatancy law of the kind of Eq. (11) was given by GDR MiDi (2004), and by Carleo et al. (2019) limited to the dense regime ($\nu > 0.4$). A disadvantage of Eq. (11) is that it may yield unphysically low values of ν for large I . Here, we propose a slightly modified EOS,

$$\nu(I) = \nu_{\min} + \frac{\nu_{\max} - \nu_{\min}}{1 + a'I}, \quad (12)$$

where $\nu_{\min} > 0$ is a lower bound and $a' = a/(\nu_{\max} - \nu_{\min})$, so that Eq. (11) is recovered for $I \ll 1$. While Eq. (12) cannot correctly describe very dilute flows, for which the EOS should depend not only on I but also on the fluctuation velocities (i.e., on the granular temperature), it yields $\nu_{\min} < \nu < \nu_{\max}$ for any value of I . In the subsequent derivation of the multilayer model, EOS (12) will be suitably rewritten in a layer-averaged discretized form (see Sec. III D 2).

III. DERIVATION OF THE MULTILAYER MODEL

The multilayer model is, here, derived by depth-averaging the mass and momentum equations for each layer and by subsequent asymptotic simplification.

A. Layering and boundary conditions

The avalanche is postulated to be composed of N layers, whose spatial domains Ω_i are numbered in ascending order from the bed toward the free surface (Fig. 1). The generic i -th layer has thickness $h_i(x, t)$. The velocity and the volume fraction in layer i are denoted with $\mathbf{u}_i(x, z, t)$ and $\nu_i(x, z, t)$, respectively.

Using a notation similar to Audusse (2011a) and Fernández-Nieto *et al.* (2016), the interface between layers i and $i + 1$ is given by

$$\Gamma_{i+1/2}(x, z, t) = z - z_{i+1/2}(x, t) = z - \sum_{j=1}^i h_j(x, t) - b(x) = 0, \quad (13)$$

where b is the bottom of the lowermost layer and $h_i(x, t) = z_{i+1/2}(x, t) - z_{i-1/2}(x, t)$. The basal and free surfaces, $\Gamma_{1/2}$ and $\Gamma_{N+1/2}$, are, respectively, $\Gamma_{1/2}(x, z, t) = z - b(x) = 0$ and $\Gamma_{N+1/2}(x, z, t) = z - b(x) - h(x, t) = 0$, with $h(x, t) = \sum_{i=1}^N h_i(x, t)$. As $\Gamma_{N+1/2}$ is a material surface, it holds

$$\frac{d\Gamma_{N+1/2}}{dt} = 0 \Rightarrow -\partial_t z_{N+1/2} - u_{x,N} \partial_x z_{N+1/2} + u_{z,N} = 0, \quad (14)$$

with $u_{x,N}$ and $u_{z,N}$ being the x and z components of the velocity in the uppermost layer, respectively. For the derivation of the model equations in the most general form, mass exchanges are allowed across the layers' interfaces. The kinematic boundary conditions (KBC), fulfilling the mass balance across $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$, read as

FIG. 1. Sketch of the multilayer approach. The interfaces between the layers, $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$, are dashed, while the basal and free surfaces, $\Gamma_{1/2}$ and $\Gamma_{N+1/2}$, are in solid lines.

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{d\Gamma_{i+1/2}}{dt} \right|^- &= \frac{M_{i+1/2}}{\rho_g \nu_i} |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}| \\ &\Rightarrow \rho_g \nu_i (-\partial_t z_{i+1/2} - u_{x,i} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} + u_{z,i}) \\ &= M_{i+1/2} |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}|, \\ \left. \frac{d\Gamma_{i+1/2}}{dt} \right|^+ &= \frac{M_{i+1/2}}{\rho_g \nu_{i+1}} |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}| \\ &\Rightarrow \rho_g \nu_{i+1} (-\partial_t z_{i+1/2} - u_{x,i+1} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} + u_{z,i+1}) \\ &= M_{i+1/2} |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}|, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $M_{i+1/2}$ is the mass flux per unit length of interface and $|\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}| = \sqrt{1 + (\partial_x z_{i+1/2})^2}$. With the chosen convention, $M_{i+1/2} > 0$ if a net mass flux goes from layer i into layer $i + 1$. As $\mathbf{u}_i(x, z, t)$ and $\nu_i(x, z, t)$ may exhibit discontinuities at the interfaces, the superscripts $+$ and $-$ in Eq. (15) indicate that such quantities are evaluated, respectively, from above and below $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$. The free surface is assumed to be traction free: i.e., $\mathbf{T}_{N+1/2} \mathbf{n}_{N+1/2} = \mathbf{0}$ at $\Gamma_{N+1/2}$. The dynamic boundary conditions (DBC) at the layers' interfaces are governed by a discrete reformulation of the $\mu(I)$ stress,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{T}_{i+1} \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} - (\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{T}_{i+1} \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2}) \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \\ = \frac{\sqrt{2} \mu(I) p_{i+1}}{\|\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^+\|} \left[\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^+ \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} - (\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^+ \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2}) \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \right], \\ \mathbf{T}_i \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} - (\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{T}_i \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2}) \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \\ = \frac{\sqrt{2} \mu(I) p_i}{\|\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^-\|} \left[\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^- \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} - (\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^- \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2}) \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} = \nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2} / |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}|$ is the unit normal vector to $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$. Using the notation by Fernández-Nieto *et al.* (2014), $\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^\pm$ represents suitable approximations of the strain-rate tensor from above and below $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$. For $M_{i+1/2} = 0$, the right-hand sides of (16) obviously need to be equal. Conversely, for $M_{i+1/2} \neq 0$ (and a non-zero velocity jump), the stress tensor exhibits a jump at $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$ that has to fulfill the Rankine–Hugoniot conditions (e.g., Sarno *et al.*, 2014),

$$\llbracket \mathbf{T} \rrbracket \mathbf{n}_{i+1/2} = \llbracket \mathbf{u} \rrbracket M_{i+1/2}, \quad (17)$$

with $\llbracket f \rrbracket = f^+ - f^-$. Suitable expressions for (16), consistent with Eq. (17), will be defined in Sec. III D 1.

The DBC at bed is identical to the first equation of Eq. (16), if the bed is made of the same granular material. Conversely, if there is a different bedrock, allowing basal slip ($\mathbf{u}_1|_{\Gamma_{1/2}} \neq \mathbf{0}$), the following modified DBC holds:

$$\mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{n}_{1/2} - (\mathbf{n}_{1/2} \cdot \mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{n}_{1/2}) \mathbf{n}_{1/2} = \mu^* p_1 \frac{\mathbf{u}_1 - (\mathbf{u}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{1/2}) \mathbf{n}_{1/2}}{|\mathbf{u}_1 - (\mathbf{u}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{1/2}) \mathbf{n}_{1/2}|}, \quad (18)$$

with μ^* being the basal friction coefficient.

B. Depth averaging of the balance equations

1. Mass balance equations

The depth-integration of the mass balance, Eq. (3), along the generic layer i reads as

$$\int_{z_{i-1/2}}^{z_{i+1/2}} [\partial_t \nu_i + \partial_x (\nu_i u_{x,i}) + \partial_z (\nu_i u_{z,i})] dz = 0. \quad (19)$$

By recursively using the Leibniz integral rule (e.g., Gray *et al.* 1999) and exploiting the KBC (14)–(15), (19) is recast as

$$\partial_t(\overline{v_i h_i}) + \partial_x(\overline{v_i u_{x,i} h_i}) = \frac{M_{i-1/2} |\nabla \Gamma_{i-1/2}|}{\rho_g} - \frac{M_{i+1/2} |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}|}{\rho_g}, \quad (20)$$

where $\overline{f_i} = (1/h_i) \int_{z_{i-1/2}}^{z_{i+1/2}} f_i dz$. It is worth anticipating that suitable constitutive laws for the mass exchanges, $M_{i\pm 1/2}$, will be required. While such mass exchanges can be theoretically calculated on a physical basis if the streamlines were exactly known, in the literature these quantities are often determined for numerical purposes: e.g., they are set equal to zero, which amounts to assuming perfectly immiscible layers (Audusse, 2005), or, conversely, they are calculated so as to enforce uniform layers' thicknesses along the flow depth, which equals to assuming the perfect permeability of the layers' interfaces toward inter-layer mass movements (Audusse *et al.* 2011a, Fernández-Nieto *et al.* 2016).

2. Depth averaging of the z component of the momentum balance equation

The z component momentum equation, Eq. (5), averaged along the layer i, reads as

$$\int_{z_{i-1/2}}^{z_{i+1/2}} \left[\partial_t(\nu_i u_{z,i}) + \partial_x(\nu u_{x,i} u_{z,i}) + \partial_z(\nu u_{z,i}^2) + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (\partial_z p_i - \partial_x t_{zx,i}^* - \partial_z t_{zz,i}^*) + \nu_i g \cos \zeta \right] dz = 0. \quad (21)$$

Using the Leibniz rule, Eq. (21) is recast as

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t(h_i \overline{v_i u_{z,i}}) + \partial_x \left(h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i} u_{z,i}} - \frac{1}{\rho_g} h_i t_{zx,i}^* \right) \\ + \left[\nu_i u_{z,i}^2 + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (p_i - t_{zz,i}^*) \right]_{z_{i-1/2}}^{z_{i+1/2}} + g \cos \zeta \overline{v_i h_i} \\ - \nu_i u_{z,i} |_{i+1/2} \partial_t z_{i+1/2} + \nu_i u_{z,i} |_{i-1/2} \partial_t z_{i-1/2} \\ - \nu_i u_{x,i} u_{z,i} |_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} + \nu_i u_{x,i} u_{z,i} |_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2} \\ + \frac{1}{\rho_g} t_{zx,i}^* |_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} - \frac{1}{\rho_g} t_{zx,i}^* |_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2} = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where the notation $|_{i\pm 1/2}$ indicates the value of the function at $z = z_{i\pm 1/2}$. Grouping all the terms involved in the KBC (15), Eq. (22) is rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t(h_i \overline{v_i u_{z,i}}) + \partial_x \left(h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i} u_{z,i}} - \frac{1}{\rho_g} h_i t_{zx,i}^* \right) \\ + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (p_i |_{i+1/2} - p_i |_{i-1/2} - t_{zz,i}^* |_{i+1/2} + t_{zz,i}^* |_{i-1/2}) + g \cos \zeta \overline{v_i h_i} \\ + u_{z,i} |_{i+1/2} \nu_i |_{i+1/2} \underbrace{(u_{z,i} |_{i+1/2} - \partial_t z_{i+1/2} - u_{x,i} |_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2})}_{=M_{i+1/2}/\rho_g |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}| \text{ for the KBC at } \Gamma_{i+1/2}} \\ - u_{z,i} |_{i-1/2} \nu_i |_{i-1/2} \underbrace{(u_{z,i} |_{i-1/2} - \partial_t z_{i-1/2} + u_{x,i} |_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2})}_{=M_{i-1/2}/\rho_g |\nabla \Gamma_{i-1/2}| \text{ for the KBC at } \Gamma_{i-1/2}} \\ + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (t_{zx,i}^* |_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} - t_{zx,i}^* |_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2}) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

whence

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t(h_i \overline{v_i u_{z,i}}) + \partial_x \left(h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i} u_{z,i}} - \frac{1}{\rho_g} h_i t_{zx,i}^* \right) \\ + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (p_i |_{i+1/2} - p_i |_{i-1/2} - t_{zz,i}^* |_{i+1/2} + t_{zz,i}^* |_{i-1/2}) \\ + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (t_{zx,i}^* |_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} - t_{zx,i}^* |_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2}) \\ = -g \cos \zeta \overline{v_i h_i} + u_{z,i} |_{i-1/2} \frac{M_{i-1/2} |\nabla \Gamma_{i-1/2}|}{\rho_g} \\ - u_{z,i} |_{i+1/2} \frac{M_{i+1/2} |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}|}{\rho_g}. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

3. Depth averaging of the x component of the momentum balance equation

The depth-averaged equation of the x component of the momentum equation, Eq. (4), reads as

$$\int_{z_{i-1/2}}^{z_{i+1/2}} \left[\partial_t(\nu_i u_{x,i}) + \partial_x(\nu_i u_{x,i}^2) + \partial_z(\nu_i u_{x,i} u_{z,i}) + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (\partial_x p_i - \partial_x t_{xx,i}^* - \partial_z t_{xz,i}^*) - \nu_i g \sin \zeta \right] dz = 0. \quad (25)$$

Thanks to the Leibniz rule and the KBC (15), Eq. (25) is recast as

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t(h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}}) + \partial_x \left(h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}^2} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho_g} \partial_x (h_i \overline{p_i} - h_i t_{xx,i}^*) - g \sin \zeta \overline{v_i h_i} \\ + u_{x,i} |_{i+1/2} \nu_i |_{i+1/2} \underbrace{(u_{z,i} |_{i+1/2} - \partial_t z_{i+1/2} - u_{x,i} |_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2})}_{=M_{i+1/2}/\rho_g |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}| \text{ for the KBC at } \Gamma_{i+1/2}} \\ - u_{x,i} |_{i-1/2} \nu_i |_{i-1/2} \underbrace{(u_{z,i} |_{i-1/2} - \partial_t z_{i-1/2} - u_{x,i} |_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2})}_{=M_{i-1/2}/\rho_g |\nabla \Gamma_{i-1/2}| \text{ for the KBC at } \Gamma_{i-1/2}} \\ + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (-p_i |_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} + p_i |_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2} \\ + t_{xx,i}^* |_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} - t_{xx,i}^* |_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2}) \\ - \frac{1}{\rho_g} t_{xz,i}^* |_{i+1/2} + \frac{1}{\rho_g} t_{xz,i}^* |_{i-1/2} = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

whence

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t(h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}}) + \partial_x \left(h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}^2} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho_g} \partial_x (h_i \overline{p_i} - h_i t_{xx,i}^*) \\ + \frac{1}{\rho_g} [(p_i |_{i-1/2} - t_{xx,i}^* |_{i-1/2}) \partial_x z_{i-1/2} \\ - (p_i |_{i+1/2} - t_{xx,i}^* |_{i+1/2}) \partial_x z_{i+1/2}] + \frac{1}{\rho_g} (t_{xz,i}^* |_{i-1/2} - t_{xz,i}^* |_{i+1/2}) \\ = g \sin \zeta \overline{v_i h_i} + u_{x,i} |_{i-1/2} \frac{M_{i-1/2} |\nabla \Gamma_{i-1/2}|}{\rho_g} \\ - u_{x,i} |_{i+1/2} \frac{M_{i+1/2} |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}|}{\rho_g}. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

C. Non-dimensionalization and scaling analysis for simplifications

Analogous to [Tai et al. \(2012\)](#) and [Sarno et al. \(2014\)](#), a long-wave approximation is employed to simplify the above depth-averaged equations. The granular avalanche is assumed to be thin, with a typical depth, H , much smaller than the typical length scale L , so that $\varepsilon = H/L \ll 1$. The following set of scalings is considered:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon &= H/L \ll 1, \quad (x, z)^T = L(\hat{x}, \varepsilon \hat{z})^T, \\ (g_x, g_z)^T &= g(\sin \zeta, -\cos \zeta)^T, \quad t = \left(\sqrt{L/g}\right) \hat{t}, \\ h_i &= H \hat{h}_i, \quad z_{i-1/2} = H \hat{z}_{i-1/2}, \quad z_{i+1/2} = H \hat{z}_{i+1/2}, \quad (28) \\ b &= H \hat{b}, \quad (u_{x,i}, u_{z,i})^T = \sqrt{gL}(\hat{u}_{x,i}, \varepsilon \hat{u}_{z,i})^T, \\ (p_i, t_{xx,i}^*, t_{zz,i}^*, t_{xz,i}^*)^T &= \rho_g g H (\hat{p}_i, \hat{\mu}_{xx,i}^*, \hat{\mu}_{zz,i}^*, \hat{\mu}_{xz,i}^*)^T, \end{aligned}$$

where the capped notation, \hat{f} , denotes the dimensionless variables. The volume fraction, already dimensionless, is $\nu_i = \hat{\nu}_i = \mathcal{O}(1)$. Since granular avalanches are generally driven by gravity and flow on an inclined bed, we chose the \sqrt{gL} scaling for $u_{x,i}$ (e.g., [Gray et al., 1999](#)) instead of the \sqrt{gH} scaling, more common in hydraulics. The friction coefficient, μ , is assumed to be $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^\beta)$ with $0 < \beta < 1$, as it influences the run-out distance of the avalanche. Considering (28) and the jump conditions (17), the mass exchanges across the interfaces scale as

$$M_{i+1/2} |\nabla \Gamma_{i+1/2}| = \rho_g \varepsilon^{1+\beta} \sqrt{gL} (\hat{M}_{x,i+1/2}), \quad (29)$$

where $\hat{M}_{x,i+1/2}$ concisely denotes the dimensionless mass flux per unit length of interface projected along x (e.g., [Sarno et al., 2014](#)) and also incorporates the volume fraction.

For simplicity, the capped notation of dimensionless quantities is dropped henceforth and the dimensional factors are collected in curly brackets $\{\}$. By virtue of (28), the mass balance, Eq. (20), is recast as

$$\left\{ \varepsilon \sqrt{gL} \right\} \left[\partial_t (\bar{\nu}_i h_i) + \partial_x (\bar{\nu}_i \overline{u_{x,i}} h_i) \right] = \left\{ \varepsilon^{1+\beta} \sqrt{gL} \right\} [M_{x,i-1/2} - M_{x,i+1/2}]. \quad (30)$$

While the mass exchanges are $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{1+\beta})$, Eq. (30) is kept in its exact form.

The dimensionless z component depth-averaged momentum equation, Eq. (24), reads as

$$\begin{aligned} \{ \varepsilon g H \} & \left[\partial_t (h_i \bar{\nu}_i \overline{u_{z,i}}) + \partial_x (h_i \bar{\nu}_i \overline{u_{x,i}} \overline{u_{z,i}}) \right] \\ & - \{ \varepsilon^{1+\beta} g H \} \partial_x (h_i \overline{t_{xz,i}^*}) + \{ g H \} (p_i|_{i+1/2} - p_i|_{i-1/2}) \\ & + \{ \varepsilon^\beta g H \} (t_{zz,i}^*|_{i-1/2} - t_{zz,i}^*|_{i+1/2}) \\ & + \{ \varepsilon^{1+\beta} g H \} (t_{zx,i}^*|_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} - t_{zx,i}^*|_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2}) \\ & = - \{ g H \} \cos \zeta \bar{\nu}_i h_i + \{ \varepsilon^{1+\beta} g H \} \\ & \times \left[u_{z,i}|_{i-1/2} M_{x,i-1/2} - u_{z,i}|_{i+1/2} M_{x,i+1/2} \right]. \quad (31) \end{aligned}$$

To the leading order $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^0)$, Eq. (31) reduces to

$$\{ g H \} \left[p_i|_{i+1/2} - p_i|_{i-1/2} + \cos \zeta \bar{\nu}_i h_i \right] = 0, \quad (32)$$

which recovers the hydrostatic pressure distribution within each layer, as in typical shallow water type models. By depth-averaging the z component momentum equation from the free surface, $z_{N+1/2}$, to the generic z , and considering the stress free DBC at the free surface, the pressure field is given by

$$\{ \rho_g g H \} p(x, z, t) = \{ \rho_g g H \} \left[\cos \zeta \sum_{i=1}^N \min \left(\bar{\nu}_i h_i(x, z, t), \max \left(0, \int_z^{z_{i+1/2}(x, z, t)} \nu_i(x, z, t) dz \right) \right) \right] + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^\beta). \quad (33)$$

Assuming $\nu_i(x, z, t) = \bar{\nu}_i(x, t)$ within each layer, (33) is simplified to

$$\begin{aligned} \{ \rho_g g H \} p(x, z, t) & = \{ \rho_g g H \} \left[\cos \zeta \sum_{i=1}^N \min \left(\bar{\nu}_i h_i, \max(0, \bar{\nu}_i (z_{i+1/2} - z)) \right) \right] + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^\beta). \quad (34) \end{aligned}$$

The x component of the depth-averaged momentum equation, Eq. (27), in dimensionless form reads as

$$\begin{aligned} \{ g H \} \partial_t (h_i \bar{\nu}_i \overline{u_{x,i}}) & + \{ g H \} \partial_x (h_i \overline{\nu_i u_{x,i}^2}) + \{ \varepsilon g H \} \partial_x (h_i \bar{p}_i) \\ & - \{ \varepsilon^{1+\beta} g H \} \partial_x (h_i \overline{t_{xx,i}^*}) \\ & + \{ \varepsilon g H \} \left[p_i|_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2} - p_i|_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} \right] \\ & - \{ \varepsilon^{1+\beta} g H \} \left[t_{xx,i}^*|_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2} - t_{xx,i}^*|_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} \right] \\ & + \{ \varepsilon^\beta g H \} \left[t_{xz,i}^*|_{i-1/2} - t_{xz,i}^*|_{i+1/2} \right] \\ & = \{ g H \} \sin \zeta \bar{\nu}_i h_i + \{ \varepsilon^\beta g H \} \\ & \times \left[u_{x,i}|_{i-1/2} M_{x,i-1/2} - u_{x,i}|_{i+1/2} M_{x,i+1/2} \right]. \quad (35) \end{aligned}$$

The first-order model can be obtained by dropping out all smaller-than- $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ terms in the x component momentum equation (e.g., [Gray et al., 1999](#)). In this fashion, Eq. (35) is simplified to

$$\begin{aligned} \{ g H \} \partial_t (h_i \bar{\nu}_i \overline{u_{x,i}}) & + \{ g H \} \partial_x (h_i \overline{\nu_i u_{x,i}^2}) + \{ \varepsilon g H \} \partial_x (h_i \bar{p}_i) \\ & + \{ \varepsilon g H \} \left[p_i|_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2} - p_i|_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2} \right] \\ & + \{ \varepsilon^\beta g H \} \left[t_{xz,i}^*|_{i-1/2} - t_{xz,i}^*|_{i+1/2} \right] \\ & = \{ g H \} \sin \zeta \bar{\nu}_i h_i + \{ \varepsilon^\beta g H \} \\ & \times \left[u_{x,i}|_{i-1/2} M_{x,i-1/2} - u_{x,i}|_{i+1/2} M_{x,i+1/2} \right], \quad (36) \end{aligned}$$

where the pressure coupling between the layers is accounted for by $\{ \varepsilon g H \} [p_i|_{i-1/2} \partial_x z_{i-1/2} - p_i|_{i+1/2} \partial_x z_{i+1/2}]$ and the quantities \bar{p}_i , $p_i|_{i-1/2}$, and $p_i|_{i+1/2}$ are obtainable from (33). The term $h_i \overline{\nu_i u_{x,i}^2}$ can be calculated by using the Boussinesq coefficient, γ_i ,

$$h_i \overline{\nu_i u_{x,i}^2} = \int_{z_{i-1/2}}^{z_{i+1/2}} \nu_i u_{x,i}^2 dz = \gamma_i (h_i \bar{\nu}_i \overline{u_{x,i}})^2 / (h_i \bar{\nu}_i). \quad (37)$$

Typically, there is a slightly negative correlation between $u_{x,i}$ and ν_i profiles due to dilatancy (e.g., [Meninno et al., 2018](#); [Carleo et al., 2019](#)). Hence, γ_i is expected to be smaller than in the case of constant volume fraction, $\overline{u_{x,i}^2}/\overline{u_{x,i}}^2$. Here, it is simply assumed $\gamma_i = 1$.

Similar to [Audusse \(2005\)](#), it is further postulated that

$$\nu_i(x, z, t) = \overline{\nu_i}(x, t) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon), \quad u_{x,i}(x, z, t) = \overline{u_{x,i}}(x, t) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon), \quad (38)$$

which amounts to assuming that the main changes in velocity and volume fraction occur at the layers' interfaces. Hence, the quantities, $u_{x,i}|_{i-1/2}$ and $u_{x,i}|_{i+1/2}$ in Eq. (36) can be approximated by $\overline{u_{x,i}}$. Moreover, with (38) holding, Eq. (34) is still valid to order $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^\beta)$ and, hence, the depth-averaged quantity $\overline{p_i}$ in Eq. (36) can be simply written as

$$\{\rho_g g H\} \overline{p_i}(x, t) = \{\rho_g g H\} \left[\cos \zeta \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \overline{\nu_j} h_j + \frac{\overline{\nu_i} h_i}{2} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^\beta) \right]. \quad (39)$$

Putting (39) into Eq. (36) and after some simplifications, the non-dimensional equations of the first-order model read as

$$\partial_t(\overline{\nu_i} h_i) + \partial_x(\overline{\nu_i} \overline{u_{x,i}} h_i) = \varepsilon^\beta (M_{x,i-1/2} - M_{x,i+1/2}), \quad (40)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_t(h_i \overline{\nu_i} \overline{u_{x,i}}) + \partial_x \left(h_i \overline{\nu_i} \overline{u_{x,i}^2} \right) + \varepsilon \cos \zeta \partial_x (\overline{\nu_i} h_i^2 / 2) \\ & + \varepsilon \cos \zeta \left[h_i \partial_x \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \overline{\nu_j} h_j \right) + h_i \overline{\nu_i} \partial_x \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} h_j + b \right) \right] \\ & = \sin \zeta \overline{\nu_i} h_i + \varepsilon^\beta \left[\overline{u_{x,i}} (M_{x,i-1/2} - M_{x,i+1/2}) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - t_{xz,i}^*|_{i-1/2} + t_{xz,i}^*|_{i+1/2} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

The partial differential equation (PDE) system (40)–(41) can be solved after defining suitable closures for $t_{xz,i}^*|_{i\pm 1/2}$, $M_{x,i\pm 1/2}$, and $\overline{\nu_i}$.

D. Closures

1. Closures for the shear stresses

Discretized formulas for the $\mu(I)$ stress, Eq. (9), at the interfaces are required for the calculation of $t_{xz,i}^*|_{i\pm 1/2}$ in Eq. (41). First, suitable approximations of \mathbf{D} , $\|\mathbf{D}\|$, and I at the interfaces have to be considered. Owing to the scalings (28), it holds

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D} &= \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 2\partial_x u_x & \partial_z u_x + \partial_x u_z \\ \partial_z u_x + \partial_x u_z & 2\partial_z u_z \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{g}{L}} \varepsilon^{-1} \right\} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon \partial_x \hat{u}_x & (\partial_z \hat{u}_x + \varepsilon^2 \partial_x \hat{u}_z) / 2 \\ (\partial_z \hat{u}_x + \varepsilon^2 \partial_x \hat{u}_z) / 2 & \varepsilon \partial_z \hat{u}_z \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{D}\| &= \sqrt{\mathbf{D} : \mathbf{D}} = \sqrt{(\partial_x u_x)^2 + \frac{(\partial_x u_z + \partial_z u_x)^2}{2} + (\partial_z u_z)^2} \\ &= \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{g}{L}} \varepsilon^{-1} \right\} \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 (\partial_x \hat{u}_x)^2 + \varepsilon^4 \frac{(\partial_x \hat{u}_z)^2}{2} + \frac{(\partial_z \hat{u}_x)^2}{2} + \varepsilon^2 (\partial_x \hat{u}_z)(\partial_z \hat{u}_x) + \varepsilon^2 (\partial_z \hat{u}_z)^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

Analogous to [Gray and Edwards \(2014\)](#), the following leading-order approximations are used:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D} &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{g}{L}} \varepsilon^{-1} \right\} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \partial_z \hat{u}_x \\ \partial_z \hat{u}_x & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^0), \\ \|\mathbf{D}\| &= \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{g}{L}} \varepsilon^{-1} \right\} \frac{|\partial_z \hat{u}_x|}{\sqrt{2}} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^0)^+, \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

with $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^0)^+$ underlining that the error is non-negative. Note that, while the approximations in (44) are $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^0)$, the resulting error in Eq. (41) is $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^\beta)$, owing to the friction coefficient in Eqs. (9)–(10). To avoid singularities of Eq. (9) for zero deformation, $|\partial_z \hat{u}_x|$ in Eq. (44) is increased by a small positive constant δ . This correction is reminiscent of the regularization by [Bercovier and Engelman \(1980\)](#), customarily employed in the context of non-Newtonian fluids with yield stress (e.g., [Martino and Papa, 2008](#)) and also adopted by [Fernández-Nieto et al. \(2016\)](#) in the context of the $\mu(I)$ rheology. The approximation of \mathbf{D} at the interface $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$, $\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}$ [cf. Eq. (16)], requires the estimation of $\partial_z u_x|_{i+1/2}$, which, holding (38), is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_z u_x|_{i+1/2} &\approx \Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2} = \frac{\overline{u_{x,i+1}} - \overline{u_{x,i}}}{(h_i + h_{i+1})/2} \\ &= \frac{h_{i+1} \overline{\nu_{i+1}} \overline{u_{x,i+1}} / h_{i+1} \overline{\nu_{i+1}} - h_i \overline{\nu_i} \overline{u_{x,i}} / h_i \overline{\nu_i}}{(h_i \overline{\nu_i} / \overline{\nu_i} + h_{i+1} \overline{\nu_{i+1}} / \overline{\nu_{i+1}}) / 2}. \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

For the non-slip KBC at the bed, a first-order extrapolation is considered,

$$\partial_z u_x|_{1/2} \approx \Delta_z u_x|_{1/2} = \frac{\overline{u_{x,1}}}{h_1/2} = \frac{h_1 \overline{\nu_1} \overline{u_{x,1}} / h_1 \overline{\nu_1}}{h_1 \overline{\nu_1} / \overline{\nu_1} / 2}. \quad (46)$$

Consequently, I at the interface reads as

$$I|_{i+1/2} = \frac{\sqrt{2} d_g \|\mathbf{D}\|}{\sqrt{p/\rho_g}} \Big|_{i+1/2} \approx \frac{\sqrt{\rho_g} d_g (|\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}| + \delta)}{\sqrt{p|_{i+1/2}}}, \quad (47)$$

where $p|_{i+1/2}$ is the pressure at $z_{i+1/2}$, obtainable from Eq. (34). Note that we chose to introduce the correction δ also in (47), so that $|\partial_z u_x|_{i+1/2}| + \delta$ exactly cancels out in the shear-rate dependent term of Eq. (9).

For the special case of zero mass exchange across $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$, the shear stress is single-valued at $\Gamma_{i+1/2}$. Namely, $\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}^\pm$ [cf. Eq. (16)] is

set equal to $\mathbf{D}_{i+1/2}$, obtainable from Eqs. (44)–(45). Consequently, the shear stress in dimensional form (also incorporating the factor ρ_g) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} t_{xz,i+1}^*|_{i+1/2} &= t_{xz,i}^*|_{i+1/2} = \left[\sqrt{2}\mu_s p|_{i+1/2} \hat{\mathbf{D}}_{i+1/2} + 2\tilde{\eta} \mathbf{D}_{i+1/2} \right]_{xz} \\ &= \mu_s p|_{i+1/2} \frac{\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}}{|\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}| + \delta} \\ &\quad + \frac{d_g(\mu_2 - \mu_s)\sqrt{\bar{p}_g}}{\left(I_0 + d_g(|\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}| + \delta) / \sqrt{p|_{i+1/2}/\rho_g} \right)} \\ &\quad \times \sqrt{p|_{i+1/2}} \Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}. \end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

Conversely, if $M_{i+1/2} \neq 0$, owing to the jump conditions (17) and the scalings (28)–(29), a shear stress jump emerges,

$$t_{xz,i+1}^*|_{i+1/2} - t_{xz,i}^*|_{i+1/2} = (\overline{u_{x,i+1}} - \overline{u_{x,i}}) M_{x,i+1/2} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{1+\beta}). \tag{49}$$

The jump can be split in a downwind fashion, which preserves the velocity of the layer that loses mass. Namely, the quantity, (49), can be entirely incorporated into the shear stress of the layer that gains mass, while the shear stress from the other side is given by (48). After some simplifications, Eq. (41) would be recast as

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t(h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}}) + \partial_x(h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}^2}) + \varepsilon \cos \zeta \partial_x(\overline{v_i} h_i^2 / 2) \\ + \varepsilon \cos \zeta \left[h_i \partial_x \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \overline{v_j} h_j \right) + h_i \overline{v_i} \partial_x \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} h_j + b \right) \right] \\ = \sin \zeta \overline{v_i} h_i + \varepsilon^\beta [u_{i-1/2,downwind} M_{x,i-1/2} \\ - u_{i+1/2,downwind} M_{x,i+1/2} - \tilde{t}_{xz}^*|_{i-1/2} + \tilde{t}_{xz}^*|_{i+1/2}], \end{aligned} \tag{50}$$

where $\tilde{t}_{xz}^*|_{i\pm 1/2}$ is the single-valued shear stress by (48), expressed in non-dimensional form, and $u_{i\pm 1/2,downwind}$ is the non-dimensional downwind velocity at $\Gamma_{i\pm 1/2}$ (if $M_{x,i+1/2} \geq 0$ $u_{i+1/2,downwind} = \overline{u_{x,i}}$, if $M_{x,i+1/2} < 0$ $u_{i+1/2,downwind} = \overline{u_{x,i+1}}$).

Finally, it is required to determine the mass exchanges, $M_{x,i\pm 1/2}$, in Eq. (50). Since in this work we primarily focus on the well-posedness of the multilayer model, for simplicity we will consider the case of vanishing mass exchanges, i.e., perfectly immiscible layers (Audusse, 2005). Hence, in the rest of the manuscript we will set $M_{x,i\pm 1/2} = 0$. Nonetheless, it is worth mentioning that, thanks to the physically based regularization that will be introduced in Sec. III E, the

model is well-posed independent from the assumptions made on the mass exchanges (see Sec. IV).

2. Closure equations for the volume fraction

In order to determine $\overline{v_i}$ in Eqs. (40)–(41), an augmented relaxation system (e.g., Liu, 1987; Chen et al., 1994) is introduced, where $\overline{v_i}$ are advected through the layers and are concurrently driven toward their equilibrium. Namely, the volume fraction field can be viewed as an order-parameter coupled with the granular flow dynamics. Following an approach similar to other models depending on an order-parameter (e.g., Aranson and Tsimring, 2002; Kamrin, 2019), the PDE system (40)–(41) is augmented with N diffusion-transport equations,

$$\tau_{relax} (\partial_t \overline{v_i} + u_i^* \partial_x \overline{v_i}) = \overline{v_i} - \overline{v_{i,EOS}} + \ell^2 \partial_{xx} \overline{v_i}, \tag{51}$$

where the new vector of the unknowns, $\mathbf{q} = (\{\overline{v_i}, \overline{v_i} h_i, \overline{v_i} u_{x,i} h_i\}_{i=1,\dots,N})^T$, also incorporates $\overline{v_i}$. In Eq. (51) u_i^* is an advection velocity of order of $\overline{u_{x,i}}$, $\overline{v_{i,EOS}}$ is the equilibrium state, i.e., the solution of the chosen EOS, τ_{relax} is the relaxation time, and ℓ is a characteristic length depending on the flow regime and on the properties of the granular material (e.g., Kamrin, 2019). The term, $\ell^2 \partial_{xx} \overline{v_i}$, is aimed at taking into account possible non-local effects. For simplicity, hereafter in this manuscript, we will set $\ell^2 = 0$.

It is worth underlining that the choice of a relaxation approach with Eq. (51) is preferable to an instantaneous-equilibrium model, in which the equilibrium values of $\overline{v_i}$, obtainable from the EOS, are directly incorporated into the momentum equations. Indeed, even if $\overline{v_i}$ are driven toward the equilibrium in very short time, the equilibrium certainly cannot be achieved instantaneously. Moreover, instantaneous-equilibrium models may cause numerical issues, as they modify the Jacobian matrix of the quasi-linear PDE system in a complex way depending on the EOS (e.g., Chen et al., 1994). If the relaxation time τ_{relax} is very small, the transport effects in Eq. (51) become negligible. In the numerical integration of the model, it will be assumed that $\tau_{relax} \leq \Delta t$ (with Δt being the time step), so that a stiff relaxation of $\overline{v_i}$ toward the equilibrium will be considered (see the Appendix A).

To be able to calculate $\overline{v_{i,EOS}}$ in Eq. (51), it is necessary to reformulate the EOS (12) for the depth-averaged quantity $\overline{v_i}$. Some approximations of the depth-averaged inertial number, which also depends on the volume fraction, are required. Using the expression (44) of $\|\mathbf{D}\|$ into Eq. (7), the following approximate formula is employed,

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{I_i}(x, t) &\approx \frac{d_g [|\overline{u_{x,i+1}} - \overline{u_{x,i-1}}| / (h_i + h_{i-1}/2 + h_{i+1}/2) + \delta]}{\sqrt{\bar{p}_i / \rho_g}} \\ &\approx \frac{d_g [h_{i+1} \overline{v_{i+1}} u_{x,i+1} / h_{i+1} \overline{v_{i+1}} - h_{i-1} \overline{v_{i-1}} u_{x,i-1} / h_{i-1} \overline{v_{i-1}}] / (h_i \overline{v_i} + h_{i-1} \overline{v_{i-1}} / 2 + h_{i+1} \overline{v_{i+1}} / 2) + \delta]}{\sqrt{\bar{p}_i / \rho_g}} \overline{v_i}, \end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

where it is assumed that $(h_i + h_{i-1}/2 + h_{i+1}/2) \approx (h_i \overline{v_i} + h_{i-1} \overline{v_{i-1}} / 2 + h_{i+1} \overline{v_{i+1}} / 2) / \overline{v_i}$. In this way, $\overline{I_i}$ only depends on $\overline{v_i}$ and not also on the volume fraction of the neighbor layers, which is

crucial to get a simple closed form for $\overline{v_{i,EOS}}$ [cf. (56)]. Since the volume fractions of the neighbor layers, $\overline{v_{i-1}}$ and $\overline{v_{i+1}}$, can be kept arbitrarily close to $\overline{v_i}$ by increasing the number of layers N , the error

from this approximation can be kept small. Moreover, as the volume fraction profiles are typically monotonic (e.g., [Meninno et al., 2018](#); [Carleo et al., 2019](#)), the small errors in estimating the terms $h_{i-1} \approx h_{i-1} \overline{v_{i-1}} / \overline{v_i}$ and $h_{i+1} \approx h_{i+1} \overline{v_{i+1}} / \overline{v_i}$ tend to compensate. For simplicity, p in (52) is depth-averaged before applying the square-root operation. The inertial number of the lowermost and uppermost layers is estimated by extrapolation of I at the nearest interface,

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{I_1}(x, t) &\approx I_{1/2}(x, t) \\ &\approx d_g \left[\frac{|\overline{u_{x,2}} - \overline{u_{x,1}}|}{(h_2 \overline{v_2} / 2 + h_1 \overline{v_1} / 2) + \delta} \right] / \sqrt{\overline{p_{1/2}} / \rho_g \overline{v_1}}, \end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{I_N}(x, t) &\approx I_{N-1/2}(x, t) \\ &\approx d_g \left[\frac{|\overline{u_{x,N}} - \overline{u_{x,N-1}}|}{(h_N \overline{v_N} / 2 + h_{N-1} \overline{v_{N-1}} / 2) + \delta} \right] / \sqrt{\overline{p_{N-1/2}} / \rho_g \overline{v_N}}. \end{aligned} \tag{54}$$

The discretized EOS reads as

$$\overline{v_{i,EOS}} = \nu_{\min} + \frac{\nu_{\max} - \nu_{\min}}{1 + a' \overline{I_i}}. \tag{55}$$

Considering that, at the equilibrium, (52)–(54) linearly depend on $\overline{v_{i,EOS}}$, Eq. (55) is a second degree equation in $\overline{v_{i,EOS}}$, with the only physically meaningful solution given by

$$\overline{v_{i,EOS}} = \frac{-1 + a' \nu_{\min} (\overline{I_i} / \overline{v_{i,EOS}}) + \sqrt{1 + (a')^2 \nu_{\min}^2 (\overline{I_i} / \overline{v_{i,EOS}})^2 - 2a' \nu_{\min} (\overline{I_i} / \overline{v_{i,EOS}}) + 4a' \nu_{\max} (\overline{I_i} / \overline{v_{i,EOS}})}}{2a' (\overline{I_i} / \overline{v_{i,EOS}})}. \tag{56}$$

E. Regularized model with the introduction of the in-plane stress gradients

A crucial improvement of the first-order multilayer model, Eqs. (40)–(41), (51), which would be otherwise ill-posed under some flow conditions (see Sec. IV), can be achieved by considering the $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{1+\beta})$ term, $-\{ \varepsilon^{1+\beta} g H \} \partial_x (h_i \overline{t_{xx,i}^*})$, which emerges from Eq. (35) and accounts for the effects of the in-plane deviatoric stresses. [Forterre \(2006\)](#) and [Gray and Edwards \(2014\)](#) found that keeping this term in one-layer depth-averaged models allows a better description of the granular roll waves. Here, an approximation of this diffusion-like term is introduced in the momentum balance equations, (41), for the main purpose of model regularization. Here, we keep $D_{xx} = \partial_x u_x$ [cf. (42)], instead of using the approximation (44). In the dimensional form, $t_{xx,i}^*$ reads as

$$\begin{aligned} t_{xx,i}^* &= \frac{\sqrt{2} \mu(I) p_i}{\|\mathbf{D}\|} D_{xx} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\|\mathbf{D}\|} \left(\frac{\mu_s}{I} + \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_s}{I_0 + I} \right) I p_i \partial_x u_{x,i} \\ &= 2 \rho_g d_g \left(\frac{\mu_s}{I} + \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_s}{I_0 + I} \right) \sqrt{p_i / \rho_g} \partial_x u_{x,i}. \end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

Some assumptions on the depth-averaged term $h_i \overline{t_{xx,i}^*} / \rho_g$ are necessary. Using the leading-order approximation $I \approx I_\zeta = \mu^{-1}(\tan \zeta)$ (e.g., [Forterre, 2006](#)), $h_i \overline{t_{xx,i}^*} / \rho_g$ can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{h_i \overline{t_{xx,i}^*}}{\rho_g} &= 2 d_g \int_{h_i} \left(\frac{\mu_s}{I} + \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_s}{I_0 + I} \right) \sqrt{p_i / \rho_g} \partial_x u_{x,i} dz \\ &\approx 2 d_g \left(\frac{\mu_s}{I_\zeta} + \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_s}{I_0 + I_\zeta} \right) \int_{h_i} \sqrt{p_i / \rho_g} \partial_x u_{x,i} dz \\ &\approx 2 d_g \left(\frac{\mu_s}{I_\zeta} + \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_s}{I_0 + I_\zeta} \right) h_i \sqrt{\overline{p_i} / \rho_g} \partial_x \overline{u_{x,i}} = \eta_{in-plane,i} \partial_x \overline{u_{x,i}}, \end{aligned} \tag{58}$$

where $\eta_{in-plane,i}$ is a depth-averaged viscosity. As $h_i \sqrt{\overline{p_i} / \rho_g} = h_i \sqrt{g \cos \zeta (\sum_{j=i+1}^N \overline{v_j} h_j + \overline{v_i} h_i / 2)}$, it follows that

$\eta_{in-plane,i} \sim h_i \sqrt{(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \overline{v_j} h_j + \overline{v_i} h_i / 2)}$, which recovers the dependence on the flow thickness to the three halves power for the special case of one layer, as in the approximation proposed by [Gray and Edwards \(2014\)](#). This similarity is interesting, especially considering that Eq. (58) has been derived without explicitly assuming a Bagnold velocity profile within each layer. Yet, a limitation of assuming $I \approx I_\zeta = \mu^{-1}(\tan \zeta)$ is that Eq. (58) only holds for $\tan^{-1} \mu_s \leq \zeta \leq \tan^{-1} \mu_2$. Conversely, by simply assuming $I \approx I_0$, $h_i \overline{t_{xx,i}^*}$ can be further approximated by

$$\frac{h_i \overline{t_{xx,i}^*}}{\rho_g} \approx d_g \frac{\mu_s + \mu_2}{I_0} h_i \sqrt{\overline{p_i} / \rho_g} \partial_x \overline{u_{x,i}}, \tag{59}$$

which has the clear computational advantage of not depending on I but underestimates $\eta_{in-plane,i}$ for $I \ll I_0$. Indeed, the depth-averaged viscosity due to in-plane stress gradients would diverge near the state of rest ([Gray and Edwards, 2014](#)). Conversely, for $I > I_0$, Eq. (59) yields only a slight overestimation of $\eta_{in-plane,i}$. Considering that the volume fraction, ν , decreases with increasing I [cf. Eq. (12)], to reduce the errors of Eq. (59), the following approximation is proposed:

$$\frac{h_i \overline{t_{xx,i}^*}}{\rho_g} \approx d_g \frac{\mu_s + \mu_2}{I_0 \nu_0} \overline{v_i} h_i \sqrt{\overline{p_i} / \rho_g} \partial_x \overline{u_{x,i}}. \tag{60}$$

In Eq. (60) ν_0 is the equilibrium value at $I = I_0$. For illustration, in [Fig. 2](#) the various approximations of $\eta_{in-plane}$, respectively, corresponding to Eqs. (58)–(60), are compared for the case of one layer with $h_1 = 1$ m. It can be noted that $\eta_{in-plane}$ is typically of order $10^{-3} - 10^{-2} \text{ m}^3 / \text{s}$ for the majority of values of I .

In summary, the viscous-like term, obtained from Eq. (60), reads as

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{\rho_s} \partial_x h_i \overline{t_{xx,i}^*} &= -\partial_x (\eta_{in-plane,i} \partial_x \overline{u_{x,i}}) \\ &= -\frac{d_g (\mu_s + \mu_2)}{I_0 \nu_0} \partial_x \left(\overline{v_i} h_i \sqrt{\overline{p_i} / \rho_g} \partial_x \overline{u_{x,i}} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

FIG. 2. Various approximations of $\eta_{in-plane}$, respectively, corresponding to expressions (58)–(60), calculated as function of I for the case of one single layer with $h_1 = 1$ m. Reference parameters for the $\mu(I)$ rheology (Jop *et al.*, 2005): $\mu_s = \tan(20.9^\circ)$, $\mu_2 = \tan(32.76^\circ)$, $l_0 = 0.279$, $d_g = 1$ mm. Reference parameters for the dilatancy law (12): $\nu_{min} = 0.1$, $\nu_{max} = 0.64$, $a' = 0.5$.

where it is assumed that $\partial_x \overline{u_{x,i}} \approx \partial_x (h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}} / h_i \overline{v_i})$. In Sec. IV, it will be shown that this approximation of the in-plane stress gradients is sufficient to ensure the model well-posedness for any value of I . This represents a major improvement over preexisting multilayer and 3D models based on the unmodified $\mu(I)$ rheology, which are only conditionally well-posed.

F. The resultant PDE system in quasi-linear form

With the incorporation of (61) into Eq. (41), the resultant PDE system, written back in dimensional form, reads as

$$\tau_{relax} (\partial_t \overline{v_i} + u_i^* \partial_x \overline{v_i}) = \overline{v_i} - \overline{v_{i,EOS}}, \tag{62}$$

$$\partial_t (h_i \overline{v_i}) + \partial_x (h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}}) = 0, \tag{63}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_t (h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}}) + \partial_x \left(\frac{(h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}})^2}{h_i \overline{v_i}} \right) + \partial_x \left(\frac{g \cos \zeta (h_i \overline{v_i})^2}{2 \overline{v_i}} \right) \\ & + g \cos \zeta \left[\frac{h_i \overline{v_i}}{\overline{v_i}} \partial_x \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \overline{v_j h_j} \right) + h_i \overline{v_i} \partial_x \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \frac{h_j \overline{v_j}}{\overline{v_j}} \right) \right] \\ & = gh_i \overline{v_i} (\sin \zeta - \cos \zeta \partial_x b) + \frac{d_g (\mu_s + \mu_2) \sqrt{g \cos \zeta}}{I_0 \nu_0} \\ & \times \partial_x \left(\overline{v_i} h_i \sqrt{\sum_{j=i+1}^N \overline{v_j h_j} + \frac{\overline{v_i} h_i}{2} \partial_x \left(\frac{h_i \overline{v_i u_{x,i}}}{h_i \overline{v_i}} \right)} \right) \\ & - \frac{1}{\rho_g} \left[t_{xz,i}^*|_{i-1/2} - t_{xz,i}^*|_{i+1/2} \right], \tag{64} \end{aligned}$$

where $\overline{v_{i,EOS}}$ in Eq. (62) is given by (56), and the shear stresses in Eq. (64) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{t_{xz,i}^*|_{i+1/2}}{\rho_g} &= \mu_s \left(g \cos \zeta \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \overline{v_j h_j} \right) \right) \frac{\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}}{|\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}| + \delta} \\ &+ \frac{d_g (\mu_2 - \mu_s)}{\left(I_0 + d_g (|\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}| + \delta) / \sqrt{g \cos \zeta \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \overline{v_j h_j} \right)} \right)} \\ &\times \sqrt{g \cos \zeta \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \overline{v_j h_j} \right)} \Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}. \tag{65} \end{aligned}$$

All the quantities in Eqs. (62)–(65) are functions of the $3N$ unknowns $\mathbf{q} = \{q_{3i-2}, q_{3i-1}, q_{3i}\}_{i=1,\dots,N}^T = \left\{ \overline{v_i}, \overline{v_i h_i}, \overline{v_i u_{x,i} h_i} \right\}_{i=1,\dots,N}^T$. The model equations, Eqs. (62)–(65), can be written in the following quasi-linear form:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{A} \partial_x \mathbf{q} &= \mathbf{s} \Rightarrow \partial_t \mathbf{q} + (\partial_q \mathbf{f} + \mathbf{A}_{non-cons}) \partial_x \mathbf{q} \\ &= \mathbf{s}_{EOS}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{s}_{topo}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{s}_{res}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{s}_{diff}(\mathbf{q}, \partial_x \mathbf{q}, \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}). \tag{66} \end{aligned}$$

The source term, \mathbf{s} , is composed of \mathbf{s}_{EOS} , resulting from the source term of Eq. (62), the topographic term, \mathbf{s}_{topo} , the resistances, \mathbf{s}_{res} , and the diffusion-like term, $\mathbf{s}_{diff}(\mathbf{q}, \partial_x \mathbf{q}, \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q})$, collecting all terms of type (61). $\mathbf{A} = \partial_q \mathbf{f} + \mathbf{A}_{non-cons}$ is a pseudo-Jacobian matrix, incorporating the Jacobian matrix of the shallow-water type conservative flux, $\partial_q \mathbf{f}$, and the matrix of non-conservative terms, $\mathbf{A}_{non-cons}$. $\partial_q \mathbf{f}$ is a $3N \times 3N$ block diagonal matrix,

$$\partial_q \mathbf{f} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{B}_1 & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{B}_2 & \mathbf{0} & \dots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \\ \dots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{B}_i & \mathbf{0} \\ & & & \ddots \\ \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{B}_N \end{pmatrix} \tag{67}$$

where

$$\mathbf{B}_i = \begin{pmatrix} u_i^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -(g \cos \zeta / 2) h_i^2 & g \cos \zeta h_i - u_i^2 & 2u_i \end{pmatrix}. \tag{68}$$

The non-conservative matrix, $\mathbf{A}_{non-cons}$, reads as

$$\mathbf{A}_{non-cons} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{C}_{1,2,upper} & \dots & \mathbf{C}_{1,N,upper} \\ \mathbf{C}_{1,1,lower} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{C}_{2,3,upper} & \dots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \\ \dots & \dots & \mathbf{C}_{i,i-1,lower} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{C}_{i,i+1,upper} \\ \vdots & & \dots & & \ddots \\ \mathbf{C}_{N,1,lower} & \dots & & \mathbf{C}_{N,N-1,lower} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \end{pmatrix}, \tag{69}$$

where the diagonal matrix blocks, $\mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3}$, are 3×3 zero matrices. The block matrices,

$$\mathbf{C}_{i,j,upper} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & g \cos \zeta h_i & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{i,j,lower} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -g \cos \zeta (h_j h_i \bar{v}_i / \bar{v}_j) & g \cos \zeta (h_i \bar{v}_i / \bar{v}_j) & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (70)$$

respectively, account for the pressure effects on the momentum balance of layer i , Eq. (64), exerted by the layer j , located above ($j > i$) and below ($j < i$). While $\mathbf{C}_{i,j,upper}$ does not depend on the index j , $\mathbf{C}_{i,j,lower}$ depends on the ratios, \bar{v}_i / \bar{v}_j and also on h_j . It can be easily verified that N eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} are equal to the transport velocities, u_i^* . Moreover, some eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} may become complex under certain flow conditions, analogous to other two-layer and multilayer models (e.g., Audusse et al., 2014; Sarno et al., 2021b). This peculiar behavior of the advection matrix, \mathbf{A} , requires an appropriate numerical solver (see the Appendix B). Nonetheless, as it will be shown in Sec. IV, the short-wave instabilities, typically arising from a hyperbolicity loss of the advective part of the PDE system, are efficiently damped out thanks to the diffusion-like terms \mathbf{s}_{diff} .

IV. SHORT-WAVE STABILITY ANALYSIS

The type of a PDE system can be evaluated by studying its characteristics. PDE systems with higher than first-order terms can be reduced to an augmented set of first-order PDEs, where the higher-order derivatives are treated as additional functions (Fletcher, 1991). For a Cauchy initial-value problem to be physically meaningful, it is necessary that the PDE system is non-elliptic, namely, that its characteristics are non-complex. A more convenient way to classify PDE systems is by a Fourier analysis in the short-wave limit (Fletcher, 1991; Joseph and Saut, 1990). Indeed, for smooth enough solutions, the ill-posedness of a PDE system is intimately related to its short-wave instability (e.g., Joseph and Saut, 1990; Woodhouse et al., 2012; Barker et al., 2015). The parabolization of conditionally hyperbolic models by introducing some diffusion is typically effective in avoiding unbounded growth rates of the short-waves (e.g., Holmås et al., 2008; Etrati and Frigaard, 2018). From a computational viewpoint, it is also desirable that the regularized model has a cutoff wavenumber for the short-wave instabilities, so as to avoid that finer meshes unveil new unstable modes. A short-wave stability analysis on the proposed multilayer model is here presented.

A. Short-wave linear stability analysis without diffusion-like terms

Here, we disregard for the moment the diffusion-like terms, \mathbf{s}_{diff} , in Eq. (66), so that \mathbf{s} does not depend on the derivatives of \mathbf{q} . A generic smooth base state, \mathbf{q}_B , which is exact solution of the PDE system and could even be an unsteady solution, is considered. Then, a small perturbation of \mathbf{q}_B , $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q}_B + \delta \mathbf{q}$ with $|\delta q_i - q_{B,i}| / |q_{B,i}| \ll 1$ is introduced. The statements below hold for any number of layers, N , thanks to the vector notation. Putting $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q}_B + \delta \mathbf{q}$ into Eq. (66), it yields

$$\partial_t (\mathbf{q}_B + \delta \mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_B + \delta \mathbf{q}) \partial_x (\mathbf{q}_B + \delta \mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{s}(\mathbf{q}_B + \delta \mathbf{q}). \quad (71)$$

First-order Taylor expansions of \mathbf{A} and of the source term, \mathbf{s} , can be compactly written as

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_B + \delta \mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_B) + \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right|_B \delta \mathbf{q} + \mathcal{O}(\|\delta \mathbf{q}\|^2),$$

$$\mathbf{s}(\mathbf{q}_B + \delta \mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{s}(\mathbf{q}_B) + \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{s}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right|_B \delta \mathbf{q} + \mathcal{O}(\|\delta \mathbf{q}\|^2), \quad (72)$$

where $\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial \mathbf{q}|_B$ is a third-order matrix with the generic element $(\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial \mathbf{q}|_B)_{n,m,l} = \partial A_{n,m} / \partial q_l|_{\mathbf{q}=\mathbf{q}_B}$. Using (72) and canceling out all zero-order terms, the $\mathcal{O}(\|\delta \mathbf{q}\|)$ -linearized PDE system reads as

$$\partial_t \delta \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_B) \partial_x \delta \mathbf{q} + \left(\left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right|_B \delta \mathbf{q} \right) \partial_x \mathbf{q}_B - \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{s}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right|_B \delta \mathbf{q} = \mathcal{O}(\|\delta \mathbf{q}\|^2). \quad (73)$$

Since \mathbf{q}_B varies spatially, the coefficients in Eq. (73) are not constant. Hence, Eq. (73) does not admit normal mode solutions with constant coefficients. Nonetheless, in the short-wave limit, the length scale of variation of $\delta \mathbf{q}$ is much smaller than the length scale of variation of \mathbf{q}_B . Thus, the coefficients of Eq. (73) can be regarded as nearly constant on a sufficiently small neighborhood $|x - x_0|$ of any spatial point x_0 (e.g., Joseph and Saut, 1990). Therefore, a normal mode solution of the type

$$\delta \mathbf{q} = \delta \tilde{\mathbf{q}}(x_0) \exp(-i\omega t + ik(x - x_0)) \quad (74)$$

is admissible in a small neighborhood of any point x_0 . Assuming that $k \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\omega = \omega_r + i\omega_i \in \mathbb{C}$ (with $i = \sqrt{-1}$), the instability corresponds to $\omega_i > 0$. Please note that this type of analysis, which can be viewed as a local stability analysis for the solution $\mathbf{q}_B(x_0)$, is not tied to a specific base state (Barker et al., 2015). Moreover, since a short-wave instability always starts as a local phenomenon, the boundary conditions of the perturbed system can be ignored (Joseph and Saut, 1990). Changing the order of matrix multiplications in the term $(\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial \mathbf{q}|_B \delta \mathbf{q}) \partial_x \mathbf{q}_B$, Eq. (73) is recast as

$$\partial_t \delta \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_B) \partial_x \delta \mathbf{q} + \left(\left(\left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right|_B \right)^{T,1-3} \partial_x \mathbf{q}_B - \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{s}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right|_B \right) \delta \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (75)$$

where the superscript $T,1-3$ in $(\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial \mathbf{q}|_B)^{T,1-3}$ means the transpose of $\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial \mathbf{q}|_B$ by switching the first and third indices. Substituting the normal modes, (74), into Eq. (75), after some simplifications, results in a linear system in $\delta \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$,

$$\left[\frac{\omega}{k} \mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_B) + \frac{i}{k} \left(\left(\left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right|_B \right)^{T,1-3} \partial_x \mathbf{q}_B - \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{s}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right|_B \right) \right] \delta \tilde{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (76)$$

which admits non-trivial solutions if and only if

$$\det \left(\frac{\omega}{k} \mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_B) + \frac{i}{k} \left(\left(\left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right|_B \right)^{T,1-3} \partial_x \mathbf{q}_B - \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{s}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right|_B \right) \right) = 0. \quad (77)$$

For $k \rightarrow \infty$, it yields

$$\det(\lambda \mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_B)) = 0, \quad (78)$$

with $\lambda = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} (\omega/k)$. Note that $\lambda = \omega/k$ are bounded, as they are eigenvalues of the finite-size matrix \mathbf{A} with real entries. It is worth noting that Eq. (78) exactly recovers the characteristic equation associated with the multilayer model without viscous regularization, which is conditionally hyperbolic. Indeed, complex conjugate eigenvalues may occur for some \mathbf{q}_B , usually characterized by Kelvin–Helmholtz or Rayleigh–Taylor instabilities (e.g., Sarno *et al.* 2021b). Holding the notation $\lambda = \lambda_r + i\lambda_i$, for $\lambda_i > 0$ the growth rate, $\omega_i = k\lambda_i$, diverges as $k \rightarrow \infty$, which corresponds to the Hadamard ill-posedness, as the solution would not depend continuously on initial data (Joseph and Saut, 1990).

B. Short-wave linear stability analysis with diffusion-like terms

By considering the diffusion-like terms, \mathbf{s}_{diff} , the short-wave stability analysis becomes dominated by these quantities involving second-order derivatives of \mathbf{q} . It can be verified that the regularization of a conditionally hyperbolic model by means of a positive definite diffusion matrix is always successful and also ensures a finite cutoff for the short-wave instabilities (Holmås *et al.*, 2008). Yet, if the diffusion matrix is only positive semidefinite, as in the case of the model (62)–(65), the well-posedness and the existence of a cutoff frequency have to be studied in detail. First, it is useful to expand the diffusion-like term, \mathbf{s}_{diff} ,

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d_g(\mu_s + \mu_2) \sqrt{g \cos \zeta}}{I_0 \nu_0} \partial_x \left(\bar{v}_i h_i \sqrt{\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j} + \frac{\bar{v}_i h_i}{2} \partial_x \left(\frac{h_i \bar{v}_i u_{x,i}}{h_i \bar{v}_i} \right) \right) \\ &= \psi \partial_x \left(q_{3i-1} \sqrt{p_{norm,i}} \left(\frac{q_{3i}}{q_{3i-1}} \right) \right) \\ &= \psi \left[\sqrt{p_{norm,i}} \partial_{xx} q_{3i} - \left(\sqrt{p_{norm,i}} q_{3i} / q_{3i-1} \right) \partial_{xx} q_{3i-1} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \partial_x \left(\sqrt{p_{norm,i}} \right) \partial_x q_{3i} - \partial_x \left(\sqrt{p_{norm,i}} q_{3i} / q_{3i-1} \right) \partial_x q_{3i-1} \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{79}$$

Here, we use the notation $\psi \equiv [d_g(\mu_s + \mu_2) \sqrt{g \cos \zeta}] / I_0 \nu_0$, $p_{norm,i} \equiv \sqrt{\sum_{j=i+1}^N \bar{v}_j h_j} + \bar{v}_i h_i / 2$ is the normalized pressure and $q_{3i-1} = \bar{v}_i h_i$ and $q_{3i} = h_i \bar{v}_i u_{x,i}$. The dominant terms in (79) are the second-order derivatives in q_{3i-1} and q_{3i} , while the other terms are

non-linear in the first-order derivatives. The pure diffusion term, $\mathbf{H} \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}$, associated with the first two terms of (79), is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H} \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q} &= \begin{pmatrix} \Psi_1 & 0 & \dots & & 0 \\ 0 & \Psi_2 & 0 & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & & \\ & \dots & 0 & \Psi_i & 0 \\ \vdots & & \dots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & & 0 & \Psi_N \end{pmatrix} \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}, \\ \Psi_i &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\psi \sqrt{p_{norm,i}} (q_{3i} / q_{3i-1}) & \psi \sqrt{p_{norm,i}} \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned} \tag{80}$$

where \mathbf{H} is a positive semidefinite matrix, since $\psi \sqrt{p_{norm,i}} > 0$. Following the same approach of Sec. IV A, we derive the $\mathcal{O}(\|\delta \mathbf{q}\|)$ -linearized PDE system associated with a small perturbation, $\delta \mathbf{q}$, around a generic base state \mathbf{q}_B . In the following expansions, which are rigorously valid for $k \rightarrow \infty$, and, hence, admit the Fourier solution of type (74), all the terms not depending on derivatives of \mathbf{q} will be neglected, since they are $\mathcal{O}(k^{-1})$. Moreover, for each coefficient of the linear expansion the leading-order terms are the highest order derivatives of \mathbf{q} , and, thus, the lower derivatives may be neglected as well (Barker *et al.*, 2015). Even so, as we are interested not only in checking the well-posedness but also in estimating the cutoff wavenumber, we keep all the terms one order lower than the highest ones. With reference to the generic layer i , the $\mathcal{O}(\|\delta \mathbf{q}\|)$ -linearized equation for Eq. (62), reads as

$$\partial_t \delta q_{3i-2} + u_i^*|_B \partial_x \delta q_{3i-2} = 0. \tag{81}$$

The $\mathcal{O}(\|\delta \mathbf{q}\|)$ -linearized equation for the mass balance, Eq. (63), is given by

$$\partial_t \delta q_{3i-1} + \partial_x \delta q_{3i} = 0. \tag{82}$$

Finally, the $\mathcal{O}(\|\delta \mathbf{q}\|)$ -linearized equation for the momentum balance, Eq. (64), reads as

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_t \delta q_{3i} - \frac{g \cos \zeta}{2} \left(\frac{q_{3i-1}}{q_{3i-2}} \right)^2 \Big|_B \partial_x \delta q_{3i-2} + \left[\frac{g \cos \zeta q_{3i-1}}{2 q_{3i-2}} - \left(\frac{q_{3i}}{q_{3i-1}} \right)^2 \right] \Big|_B \partial_x \delta q_{3i-1} + 2 \frac{q_{3i}}{q_{3i-1}} \Big|_B \partial_x \delta q_{3i} g \cos \zeta \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \left(-\frac{q_{3i-1} q_{3j-1}}{q_{3j-2}} \Big|_B \partial_x \delta q_{3j-2} + \frac{q_{3i-1}}{q_{3j-2}} \Big|_B \partial_x \delta q_{3j-1} \right) \\ & + g \cos \zeta \frac{q_{3i-1}}{q_{3i-2}} \Big|_B \sum_{j=i+1}^N \partial_x \delta q_{3j-1} + \psi \sqrt{p_{norm,i}} \frac{q_{3i}}{q_{3i-1}} \Big|_B \partial_{xx} \delta q_{3i-1} - \psi \sqrt{p_{norm,i}} \Big|_B \partial_{xx} \delta q_{3i} \\ & + \psi \left[\frac{1}{4 \sqrt{p_{norm,i}}} \Big|_B \left(-\partial_x q_{3i,B} + \frac{q_{3i}}{q_{3i-1}} \Big|_B \partial_x q_{3i-1,B} + 2 \frac{q_{3i}}{q_{3i-1}} \Big|_B \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \partial_x q_{3j-1,B} + \frac{\partial_x q_{3i-1,B}}{2} \right) \right) \right] \Big|_B \partial_x \delta q_{3i-1} \\ & + \psi \frac{\sqrt{p_{norm,i}}}{q_{3i-1}} \Big|_B \left(\partial_x q_{3i,B} - 2 \frac{q_{3i}}{q_{3i-1}} \Big|_B \partial_x q_{3i-1,B} \right) \\ & + \psi \left[\frac{1}{2 \sqrt{p_{norm,i}}} \Big|_B \left(\sum_{j=i+1}^N \partial_x q_{3j-1,B} + \frac{\partial_x q_{3i-1,B}}{2} \right) + \frac{\sqrt{p_{norm,i}}}{q_{3i-1}} \Big|_B \partial_x q_{3i-1,B} \right] \Big|_B \partial_x \delta q_{3i} \\ & + \psi \frac{1}{2 \sqrt{p_{norm,i}}} \Big|_B \left[\frac{q_{3i}}{q_{3i-1}} \Big|_B \partial_x q_{3i-1,B} - \partial_x q_{3i,B} \right] \sum_{j=i+1}^N \partial_x \delta q_{3j-1} = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{83}$$

In Eq. (83), the leading-order terms are the ones due to the pure diffusion: $\psi \sqrt{p_{norm,i}} \frac{q_{3i}}{q_{3i-1}} |_{\mathbf{B}} \partial_{xx} \delta q_{3i-1} - \psi \sqrt{p_{norm,i}} |_{\mathbf{B}} \partial_{xx} \delta q_{3i}$. Equation (83) also includes lower-order terms, coming from the advective part of Eq. (66) and from the products of derivatives [cf. (79)]. Putting the normal mode solution (74) into Eq. (83) and after some simplifications, the resulting eigenvalue problem is written as

$$\lambda \delta \tilde{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{M} \delta \tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \tag{84}$$

with $\lambda = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} (\omega/k)$. The matrix \mathbf{M} reads as

$$\mathbf{M} = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{Y}_1^{lin} & \mathbf{C}_{1,2,upper}^{lin} & \dots & & \mathbf{C}_{1,N,upper}^{lin} \\ \mathbf{C}_{1,1,lower}^{lin} & \mathbf{Y}_2^{lin} & \mathbf{C}_{2,3,upper}^{lin} & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & & \\ \dots & \dots & \mathbf{C}_{i,j-1,lower}^{lin} & \mathbf{Y}_i^{lin} & \mathbf{C}_{i,j+1,upper}^{lin} \\ \vdots & & \dots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_{N,1,lower}^{lin} & \dots & & \mathbf{C}_{N,N-1,lower}^{lin} & \mathbf{Y}_N^{lin} \end{pmatrix}, \tag{85}$$

where the blocks matrices are

$$\mathbf{Y}_i^{lin} = \begin{pmatrix} u_{i,\mathbf{B}}^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -\frac{g \cos \zeta}{2} h_{i,\mathbf{B}}^2 & g \cos \zeta h_i - u_i^2 + \Psi \sqrt{p_{norm,i,\mathbf{B}}} u_i k i + \varsigma_{i,1} & 2u_i - \Psi \sqrt{p_{norm,i,\mathbf{B}}} k i + \varsigma_{i,2} \end{pmatrix}, \tag{86}$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{i,j,upper}^{lin} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & g \cos \zeta h_{i,\mathbf{B}} + \varsigma_{i,3} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{i,j,lower}^{lin} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -g \cos \zeta h_j h_i \overline{v}_i / \overline{v}_j |_{\mathbf{B}} & g \cos \zeta h_i \overline{v}_i / \overline{v}_j |_{\mathbf{B}} & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

In Eq. (86), the quantities $\varsigma_{i,1}$, $\varsigma_{i,2}$, and $\varsigma_{i,3}$ concisely stand for the $\mathcal{O}(k^0)$ -terms resulting from the products of derivatives [cf. Eq. (83)]. Although the structure of \mathbf{Y}_i^{lin} , $\mathbf{C}_{i,j,upper}^{lin}$, $\mathbf{C}_{i,j,lower}^{lin}$ is similar to \mathbf{B}_i , $\mathbf{C}_{i,j,upper}$, $\mathbf{C}_{i,j,lower}$ of the pseudo-Jacobian matrix \mathbf{A} of Eq. (66), it can be noted that here the dominant terms scale as $\sim ki$.

1. Well-posedness

For the well-posedness, it is necessary that, as $k \rightarrow \infty$, all the imaginary parts of the eigenvalues, λ_i , are either non-positive or tend to 0 at a rate not slower than $\sim 1/k$. Since the linearized transport equations, Eq. (81), are decoupled from the other perturbation fields and always bring real eigenvalues, \mathbf{M} can be conveniently reduced to a $2N \times 2N$ matrix only taking into account the linearized Eqs. (82)–(83). Nonetheless, due to its large size, it is difficult to study the eigenvalue problem analytically. Hence, we adopt a numerical approach.

The space of the solutions was numerically investigated by considering a large number of random values of $\mathbf{q}_{\mathbf{B}}$ and $\partial_x \mathbf{q}_{\mathbf{B}}$. Specifically, the cases with 3, 5, and 10 layers and the following intervals,

$$\nu_i \in [0.1, 0.64], \quad h_i \in [10^{-3}, 1\text{m}], \quad u_i \in [-50\text{m/s}, 50\text{m/s}], \tag{87}$$

were investigated. In addition, ζ was randomly varied between 0° and 60° . With the aim of evaluating the effects of the proposed regularization on a large variety of states, involving both Kelvin–Helmholtz and Rayleigh–Taylor instabilities, in this numerical investigation ν_i are made to randomly vary by disregarding the EOS. In the practical cases,

$\partial_x \mathbf{q}_{\mathbf{B}}$ is typically small owing to the shallowness of the avalanche but sharp gradients may occur at the avalanche front. In this investigation, the quantities $\partial_x \mathbf{q}_{\mathbf{B}}$ were systematically studied in the range $[-10, 10]$ and also a few extra tests were performed with larger values up to 10^3 . The diffusion coefficient, ψ , was calculated using the same parameters of Fig. 2. For each of the three models (with 3, 5, and 10 layers), 10^5 random states of $\mathbf{q}_{\mathbf{B}}$ and $\partial_x \mathbf{q}_{\mathbf{B}}$ were generated, and the well-posedness was verified for all the investigated states. We found that spurious imaginary terms may arise in the eigenvalues calculations, as the condition number of \mathbf{M} increases with k . To avoid this issue, the precision of the numerical calculations was increased up to 100 digits, when the standard double precision was found insufficient (i.e., in cases with $|\lambda_i|$ smaller than the machine epsilon).

For small values of $\partial_x \mathbf{q}_{\mathbf{B}}$ (of order of 10^{-3}), a cutoff wavenumber was systematically found. Namely, in our numerical investigation we always found (via a bisection algorithm) the existence of a value k^* such that $\lambda_i \leq 0$ for $k \geq k^*$. Conversely, for large values of $\partial_x \mathbf{q}_{\mathbf{B}}$, corresponding to strongly unsteady states, no cutoff was observed. Nonetheless, in such cases the well-posedness was always guaranteed by bounded growth rates, $\omega_i = \lambda_i k$. In practice, we numerically checked that the changes of ω_i steadily decrease with increasing k . These numerical findings confirm the model well-posedness for the investigated cases with 3, 5, and 10 layers. It is reasonable to expect that the well-posedness also holds for a higher number of layers N , since the structure of the eigenvalue problem (84) remains essentially unchanged with increasing N .

2. Estimation of the cutoff wavelengths for spatially uniform states

The above investigation revealed the existence of a cutoff for the short-wave instabilities, as $\partial_x \mathbf{q}_B$ becomes small enough. Here, we report a further numerical study on the subset of base states, \mathbf{q}_B , with $\partial_x \mathbf{q}_B = \mathbf{0}$, which encompasses all spatially uniform unsteady and steady states of the PDE system, (66). To estimate the cutoff wavelengths, we numerically studied the eigenvalue problem (84) for 10^4 random states, obtained with $\partial_x \mathbf{q}_B = \mathbf{0}$ and with the variables varying in the same ranges of (87). This investigation on spatially uniform states can be regarded as a generalization of the inviscid Kelvin–Helmholtz (IKH) stability analysis, which is typically performed on the uniform steady states (e.g., Barnea and Taitel, 1993). The frequencies of appearance of the cutoff wavelengths, $2\pi/k$, for the 3-, 5-, and 10-layer models are reported in Fig. 3, where the states, already stable for all wavelengths (i.e., the ones with all real eigenvalues of \mathbf{A}), are not considered.

From Fig. 3, it can be seen that the distributions of the cutoff are very similar to each other and exhibit a lognormal shape. The vast majority of $2\pi/k_{cutoff}$ lie between 10^{-3} m and 10^{-1} m, with median values equal to 0.022, 0.024, and 0.016 m, respectively, for the 3-, 5-, and 10-layer cases. It is interesting to note that these values of $2\pi/k_{cutoff}$ are comparable with the typical mesh sizes, employed in standard numerical simulations (i.e., usually $\Delta x \approx 10^{-3} - 10^{-1}$ m, cf. Sec. V). A practical and important implication of this finding is that the mesh refinements, normally employed in the numerical integration of the model, are not expected to progressively unveil new unstable modes (since the growth rates below the cutoff wavelength are negative), and hence, a stable numerical convergence is achievable in practice. The actual achievement of the numerical convergence is confirmed by the results, subsequently reported in Sec. V.

Focusing on how the cutoff wavelengths vary with decreasing velocities, we performed further numerical tests, limited to the three-layer case, by progressively reducing the range of variation of the velocities in (87) from $\max|u_i| = 10^2$ m/s to $\max|u_i| = 10^{-3}$ m/s, while ν_i were kept

FIG. 3. Frequency of occurrence of the cutoff wavelengths, $2\pi/k_{cutoff}$ (dataset composed of 10^4 spatially uniform random states with $\nu_i \in [0.1, 0.64]$, $h_i \in [10^{-3}, 1\text{m}]$, $u_i \in [-50\text{m/s}, 50\text{m/s}]$, $\zeta \in [0^\circ, 60^\circ]$), inset: density function.

free to vary. When the velocity differences among the layers become small, the Kelvin–Helmholtz instabilities eventually disappear and only the Rayleigh–Taylor instabilities are made possible by the random ν_i profiles. Figure 4 reports the median values of $2\pi/k_{cutoff}$ as function of $\max|u_i|$. It can be observed that the cutoff wavelengths steadily decrease with decreasing $\max|u_i|$ and become smaller than 10^{-4} m for $\max|u_i| < 10^{-2}$ m/s. Interestingly, this finding reveals that the cutoff is strongly influenced by the off diagonal coefficients in the diffusion matrix, \mathbf{H} [cf. (80)], whose magnitudes in turn depend on the layers’ velocities. On the other hand, it shows that, for the special case of \mathbf{q}_B with zero velocities and a non-uniform volume fraction profile, the proposed regularization would be unable to provide a finite cutoff for the short-wave instabilities. Nonetheless, it is worth underlining that this occurrence is only ideal, because in real granular flows, as the velocity field vanishes, ν_i tends to a constant profile, correspondingly to the volume fraction at deposit. To study this more realistic case, additional random states were numerically generated with the same values of $\max|u_i|$ and by enforcing $\nu_i = 0.64$ for all layers. The results, from these further generations with $\nu_i = 0.64$, are also reported in Fig. 4 and exhibit a median value of the cutoff frequency of $\approx 0.02\text{m}$, almost independent from $\max|u_i|$.

3. Comparison with different regularization approaches based on artificial diffusion

To further underline the importance of the off diagonal coefficients in the diffusion matrix, \mathbf{H} , here we briefly compare the proposed model, Eq. (66), with an alternative model, where a small artificial diffusion, ψ' , is introduced in the momentum equations. With this alternative approach, similar to that discussed by Holmås et al. (2008) in the context of two-layer models, the PDE system, (66), would be modified as

$$\partial_t \mathbf{q} + (\partial_x \mathbf{f} + \mathbf{A}_{non-cons}) \partial_x \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{s}_{EOS}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{s}_{topo}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{s}_{res}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{H}' \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}. \tag{88}$$

FIG. 4. Median values of $2\pi/k_{cutoff}$ as function of $\max|u_i|$ (three-layer model). For each value of $\max|u_i|$, two datasets of 10^3 spatially uniform random states were generated, alternatively with random values $\nu_i \in [0.1, 0.64]$ and with a constant value $\nu_i = 0.64$.

Namely, in Eq. (88) the term, $\mathbf{s}_{diff}(\mathbf{q}, \partial_x \mathbf{q}, \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q})$ is substituted by the pure diffusion term,

$$\mathbf{H}' \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q} = \begin{pmatrix} \Psi' & 0 & \dots & & 0 \\ 0 & \Psi' & 0 & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & & \\ \dots & 0 & \Psi' & 0 & \\ \vdots & \dots & \dots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & & 0 & \Psi' \end{pmatrix} \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}, \quad (89)$$

$$\Psi' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \psi' \end{pmatrix}, \quad \psi' > 0.$$

In spite that, different from $\mathbf{s}_{diff}(\mathbf{q}, \partial_x \mathbf{q}, \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q})$, the regularization term $\mathbf{H}' \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}$ is not physically based, one might be tempted to prefer the PDE system, (88), over Eq. (66), for its easier numerical integration, as \mathbf{H}' is a constant diagonal matrix. While the alternative model, (88), also ensures that the wave growths are bounded for $k \rightarrow \infty$, different from the proposed model (66), it exhibits no cutoff for the short-wave instabilities, no matter how large is the artificial diffusion, ψ' . Incidentally, we observed the same inferior behavior of Eqs. (88)–(89) also by alternatively introducing a constant artificial diffusion in the mass balance equations instead of in the momentum equations, i.e., by using

$$\Psi' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \psi' & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \psi' > 0. \quad (90)$$

V. NUMERICAL TESTS

Two numerical examples are reported here to illustrate the main features of the multilayer model, (66), and its computational costs. The numerical scheme is detailed in Appendix B.

A. Uniform steady states

Here, the well-posed multilayer model is shown to be able to correctly reproduce the steady uniform Bagnold profiles (Bagnold, 1954; GDR MiDi, 2004) for all admissible slopes. In the absence of sidewall resistances, uniform flows may develop, if the bed inclination angle ζ meets the condition $\arctan \mu_s \leq \zeta < \arctan \mu_2$. In uniform flows, the inertial number is constant along the flow depth, $I_{uniform}(\zeta) = I_0 (\tan \zeta - \mu_s) / (\mu_2 - \tan \zeta)$. In addition, the volume fraction, $\nu_{uniform}(\zeta)$, is constant and can be calculated by the EOS (12). Hence, with reference to a no-slip basal KBC, the uniform velocity profile, as by the $\mu(I)$ rheology, reads as

$$u_x(z) = \frac{2}{3d_g} I_{uniform}(\zeta) \sqrt{\nu_{uniform}(\zeta) g \cos \zeta} (h^{3/2} - (h-z)^{3/2}). \quad (91)$$

For the numerical simulations reported below, the parameters of the $\mu(I)$ rheology (Jop *et al.*, 2005) are the same as used in Fig. 2: $\mu_s = \tan(20.9^\circ)$, $\mu_2 = \tan(32.76^\circ)$, $I_0 = 0.279$, and $d_g = 1$ mm. The parameters of the EOS are $\nu_{min} = 0.1$, $\nu_{max} = 0.64$, and $a' = 0.5$. The spatial domain reads $x \in [-1, 1]$ m with nonreflecting boundary conditions at $x = -1$ m and $x = 1$ m, where different simulations were carried out over the entire range of bed inclinations admissible for the steady state. The initial conditions are

$$\sum_{i=1}^N h_i(x, 0) = 0.1 \text{ m}, \quad \bar{u}_i(x, 0) = 0, \quad \bar{\nu}_i(x, 0) = 0.64. \quad (92)$$

The simulations, carried out with 20 layers of equal initial thickness 0.005 m, were run until the steady state was sensibly reached, i.e., after a time interval typically between 100 s and 2000 s found to increase with ζ . A spatial discretization with $\Delta x = 0.1$ m was employed together with a time step of $\Delta t = 0.002$ s, which was preliminarily verified to fulfill the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition for all the investigated runs. The numerical and analytical profiles, corresponding to $\zeta = 22^\circ$, $\zeta = 26^\circ$, and $\zeta = 30^\circ$, are reported in Fig. 5.

Excellent agreement between the velocity profiles is found for all bed inclinations [Fig. 5(a)]. Yet, it is worth mentioning that the numerical profiles do not exactly converge to the analytical solutions,

FIG. 5. Comparisons between the steady uniform analytical profiles (black continuous lines) and the numerical ones by the multilayer model (color markers): (a) stream-wise velocity and (b) volume fraction.

Eq. (91), due to the employed regularization of $\|\mathbf{D}\|$ (Bercovier and Engelman, 1980), and also due to the extrapolations of the averaged I at the extreme layers [cf. Eqs. (53)–(54)]. Incidentally, because of the $\|\mathbf{D}\|$ regularization, the granular material does not remain in a rigorous state of rest for $\zeta \leq \arctan(\mu_s)$ but exhibits a very slow creep flow of little practical relevance (Fernández-Nieto et al., 2016). As expected, the flow depths slightly increase with ζ , owing to dilatancy. Overall, also the volume fraction profiles are in very good agreement with the analytical ones [Fig. 5(b)], with only minor discrepancies at the bed and near the free surface. We believe that these small deviations are caused again by the extrapolations of the shear rates and by the $\|\mathbf{D}\|$ regularization.

This numerical investigation confirms that the well-posed multilayer model is able to yield physically consistent steady state profiles for all bed slopes up to $\zeta \rightarrow \arctan\mu_2$. This is a key advantage, over 3D and multilayer models, based on the unmodified $\mu(I)$ rheology, which are well-posed, and hence numerically stable, only for a narrower interval of ζ and I (Barker et al., 2015; Fernández-Nieto et al. 2016).

B. Collapse of a granular column

Here, we test the multilayer model on a problem with non-smooth initial data, the collapse of a granular column (e.g., Lube et al., 2005). The spatial domain is $x \in [-1, 1]$ m and nonreflecting boundary conditions are considered at $x = -1$ m and $x = 1$ m. The initial conditions are

$$\sum_{i=1}^N h_i(x, 0) = \begin{cases} 0.2 \text{ m,} & \text{if } -0.15 \text{ m} \leq x \leq 0.15 \text{ m} \\ 0 \text{ m,} & \text{elsewhere,} \end{cases} \quad (93)$$

$$\bar{u}_i(x, 0) = 0, \quad \bar{v}_i(x, 0) = 0.64.$$

The simulation was run with 40 layers, having an equal initial thickness of 0.005 m and $\Delta x = 1/400$ m. In the main simulation and also in the other ones reported in Sec. VB 1, the time steps were obtained by setting $\text{CFL} = 0.95$. The parameters of the $\mu(I)$ rheology and of the dilatancy law are the same of Sec. VA. The numerical results are reported in Fig. 6. The uppermost plot in each panel illustrates the

FIG. 6. Collapse of a granular column: evolution of $h_i, z_{i+1/2}$ and of the velocity and volume fraction fields, obtained with $\Delta x = 1/400$ m, 40 layers, $\text{CFL} = 0.95$, (a) $t = 0.1$ s, (b) $t = 0.25$ s, (c) $t = 0.5$ s, and (d) $t = 1$ s.

FIG. 7. The evolution of the L^1 -norm relative errors (a) and L^∞ -norm errors (b) with the mesh refinement at $t = 0.5$ s.

evolution of the flow depth, h , and of the interfaces, $z_{i+1/2}$. Figure 6 also shows the x component velocity and the volume fraction fields, reconstructed by linear interpolation of the data obtained from the various layers. For ease of representation, the color gradients, used to describe the ν field, are limited by the lower clipping value of 0.48, while a small number of computational cells near the granular fronts are found to exhibit even smaller ν , due to the high shear rate.

Though a quantitative comparison with experiments is beyond the scope of this paper, it is interesting to note that the model is able to capture non-trivial features of the granular collapse. In particular, it well describes the presence of an active surface layer superimposed on an almost static wedge, whose extension progressively increases with time (e.g., Lube et al., 2005), and the double curvature of the final deposit profile, experimentally observed for large enough initial aspect ratios of the column (Lajeunesse et al., 2004).

1. Numerical convergence and computational costs

To study the numerical convergence and the computational costs, different simulations with mesh sizes from $\Delta x = 1/50$ m to $\Delta x = 1/3200$ m were carried out using $N = 40$. In addition, various simulations with different N , ranging from 3 to 160, were performed by keeping $\Delta x = 1/400$ m. To compare the numerical solutions, obtained with different Δx and N , we evaluated the L^1 - and L^∞ -norm errors of the relevant quantities: total mass $m_{tot} = \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{v}_i h_i$, total

momentum $q_{tot} = \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{v}_i \bar{u}_{x,i} h_i$ and flow depth $h = \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{v}_i h_i / \bar{v}_i$. The L^1 -norm relative error of a generic grid function, Q^j , at the time point j , with respect to the reference solution $Q^j_{reference}$, is defined by $\sum_{r=1}^P |Q^j_r - Q^j_{reference,r}| / \sum_{r=1}^P |Q^j_{reference,r}|$, with P being the total number of computational cells. The L^∞ -norm error is given by $\max_r |Q^j_r - Q^j_{reference,r}|$ (e.g., LeVeque, 2004). For the grid convergence, the simulation with $\Delta x = 1/3200$ m is taken as reference, while, for the convergence with the number of layers N , the reference solution is the one with $N = 160$. The evolution of the L^1 - and L^∞ -norm errors with the mesh refinement is reported in Fig. 7.

Conversely, Fig. 8 illustrates the errors at different N . As shown by Figs. 7 and 8, the numerical solution behaves regularly in all norms with both increasing $1/\Delta x$ and N . Specifically, the L^1 errors are found to numerically converge as $\sim 1/\Delta x^{1.59}$ for q_{tot} and as $\sim 1/\Delta x^{1.10}$ for m_{tot} and h [Fig. 7(a)]. The L^∞ errors numerically converge as $\sim 1/\Delta x^{2.35}$ for q_{tot} and as $\sim 1/\Delta x^{1.39}$ for m_{tot} and h [Fig. 7(b)]. Similarly, the numerical convergence rates with increasing N are ≈ 1.33 in the L^1 -norm for all investigated quantities [Fig. 8(a)] and slightly smaller than 1 in the L^∞ -norm [Fig. 8(b)]. The above results confirm the excellent numerical stability of the model, made possible by its well-posedness.

To this regard, we underline that alternative numerical solutions, obtained by switching off the diffusion-like terms \mathbf{s}_{diff} , exhibit unphysical oscillations and eventually blow up, as the mesh is refined. In particular, while the well-posed model yields robust numerical results

FIG. 8. The evolution of the L^1 -norm relative errors (a) and L^∞ -norm errors (b) with the number of layers at $t = 0.5$ s.

independent from the mesh size, for the ill-posed simulations without s_{diff} , we observed oscillations of the layers' interfaces from $\Delta x = 1/400\text{m}$. As expected, these artificial oscillations become progressively stronger with $\Delta x = 1/800\text{m}$ and finer meshes. As the grain size is $d_g = 1\text{mm}$ in our numerical investigation, the onset of the numerical instabilities roughly corresponds to $\Delta x \approx 3d_g$. While such a threshold may be slightly underestimated due to the numerical diffusion intrinsic in the numerical scheme, it is remarkable that a similar threshold of a few grain diameters was also observed in [Martin et al. \(2017\)](#), where 3D models, implementing the $\mu(I)$ rheology and, alternatively, also a simpler Drucker–Prager rheology with a constant viscosity ([Ionescu et al. 2015](#)), were used to describe granular column collapses.

The computation times, obtained on an Intel Core i7–9700K@3.60 GHz processor, are reported in [Fig. 9](#). For $\Delta x \geq 1/800\text{m}$, the computation times increase with $\sim (1/\Delta x)^2$ [[Fig. 9\(a\)](#)], analogous to that expected for strictly hyperbolic models without diffusion. However, for $1/3200\text{m} \leq \Delta x < 1/800\text{m}$ the computational costs are found to increase with $\sim (1/\Delta x)^{2.25}$, owing to the increasing overhead of the time-marching algorithm accounting for the diffusion-like terms, s_{diff} (cf. [Appendix B](#)). For extremely fine meshes, the computational costs may become significantly higher than in an ideal hyperbolic model without diffusion. This limitation may be partially overcome by employing higher-order solvers. Moreover, since the structure of the PDE system (66) is suitable to be treated by graphics processing unit (GPU) based parallel algorithms (e.g., [Ko et al., 2021](#)), we foresee the potential for a substantial improvement of the computational efficiency by using a parallel computational approach.

Finally, the runtimes are found to increase with $\sim N^{0.46}$ for $N < 40$, and almost linearly for $N \geq 40$ [[Fig. 9\(b\)](#)]. This feature of the multilayer approach represents a significant computational advantage over 3D models and is made possible by the fact that the time step essentially does not depend on N (cf. [Appendix B](#)).

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a well-posed multilayer model for dry granular flows. The model incorporates the $\mu(I)$ rheology ([Jop et al., 2005](#); [Jop et al., 2006](#)) and implements a dilatancy law, derived as a generalization of the formula proposed by [da Cruz et al. \(2005\)](#). Assuming that the spatial domain of the avalanche is partitioned into a preset number of layers, the model equations were derived by depth-

averaging the mass and momentum balances along each layer and simplified by subsequent long-wave asymptotic approximation, leading to the hydrostatic pressure distribution. A well-known issue of the multilayer models is their conditional hyperbolicity, which is related to catastrophic Hadamard instabilities under certain flow conditions (e.g., [Sarno et al. 2021b](#)). To overcome this crucial limitation, which is also relevant for numerical applications, suitable approximations of the in-plane stress gradients, emerging from the $\mu(I)$ rheology ([Forterre, 2006](#); [Gray and Edwards, 2014](#)), are introduced in the first-order momentum equations. A short-wave linear stability analysis showed that these small terms, having a diffusion-like behavior, are able to sufficiently guarantee the model well-posedness and also yield finite cutoff wavelengths for the short-wave instabilities, which are typically comparable with the mesh sizes used in numerical simulations. The proposed model in its most general form allows mass exchanges across the layers. Nonetheless, it was shown that it is able to yield stable numerical results even in the limiting case of perfectly immiscible layers. Some numerical tests illustrated the excellent capabilities of the model to describe the steady state Bagnold profiles in the entire range of admissible slopes (up to $\zeta \rightarrow \arctan \mu_2$) and confirmed its numerical convergence with mesh refinement and increasing number of layers. While the additional diffusion-like terms represent a computational overhead compared to strictly hyperbolic models, it should be noted that the multilayer model is more computationally efficient than fully 3D models, especially considering that the runtimes were found to increase at most linearly with the number of the layers. Moreover, it is worth emphasizing that, different from the Navier–Stokes model with the unmodified $\mu(I)$ rheology ([Barker et al., 2015](#)), the proposed model is well-posed for any value of the inertial number and, thus, can be safely used on irregular topographies with arbitrary slopes.

Discussing about the possible limitations and future developments of the model, it should be noted that the assumption of a hydrostatic pressure distribution might be inadequate to describe granular flows with high curvatures of the streamlines (e.g., the initial stages of dam-break flows or the flow interaction with a barrier). Future experimental investigations will be useful to determine to which extent the hydrostatic assumption, also in common with the majority of depth-averaged models in the literature, is acceptable for applications. Another possible limitation of the model is represented by the range of applicability of the employed $\mu(I)$ rheology and dilatancy law, which have been validated for the intermediate dense regime ([da Cruz et al., 2005](#);

FIG. 9. Computational costs by varying the mesh size (a) and the number of layers (b).

Jop *et al.*, 2006) but are less suitable to correctly describe very slow (quasi-static) and very dilute flows (e.g., Jop, 2015). In geophysical flows on steep slopes, a very dilute surface flow, characterized by low volume fraction and chiefly collisional momentum exchanges, may develop on top of a dense granular avalanche (e.g., Savage, 1984; Ancy, 2001; Doyle *et al.*, 2011). Comparisons with experiments could help to understand if the proposed model is able to describe the essential physics of a granular avalanche, even in the presence of an upper dilute layer, and to which extent the employed dilatancy law is valid. Another aspect, which is worth being further investigated, is the choice of appropriate closures for the mass exchanges among the layers. In the present work, primarily focused on the model well-posedness, we reported a short-wave stability analysis, whose results are independent from the mass exchanges, given that the corresponding closures do not depend on the spatial derivatives of the solution. Accordingly, the reported numerical tests showed that the model yields robust results even in the extreme case of zero mass exchanges. Nonetheless, we recognize that allowing small mass exchanges among the layers could be useful to avoid an unphysical partitioning of the flow domain that may become inconvenient under some circumstances, e.g., if one layer locally becomes extremely thin compared to the neighbor ones. Finally, a detailed calibration of the model parameters and comparisons with experimental data will be presented in a separate paper.

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APPENDIX A: SUB-CHARACTERISTIC CONDITIONS OF THE RELAXATION MODEL

Here, the sound speeds of the advective part of the relaxation model, Eq. (66), i.e., $\partial_t \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{A} \partial_x \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}$, are numerically compared with the ones of the reduced equilibrium model, namely, the zero-order time-expansion model obtained by putting the \bar{v}_i of the discretized EOS (56) directly into the momentum equations, Eq. (64). Indeed, to be able to use a standard CFL condition on Δt together with a stiff relaxation of \bar{v}_i [in Eq. (62)], the sub-characteristic conditions have to be verified (Chen *et al.*, 1994).

The following sub-characteristic conditions on the extreme eigenvalues serve to guarantee that the information speed of the equilibrium system does not exceed the one of the relaxation model,

$$\min(\lambda_{i,relax}) \leq \min(\lambda_{i,equil}), \quad \max(\lambda_{i,relax}) \geq \max(\lambda_{i,equil}), \quad (A1)$$

where $\lambda_{i,relax}$ and $\lambda_{i,equil}$ are the eigenvalues of the relaxation and equilibrium systems, respectively. For strictly hyperbolic conservation laws Chen *et al.* (1994) also identified additional sub-characteristic conditions, which consist in the interlacement of the intermediate sound speeds of the two models and are associated with the dissipativity property of the first-order model obtainable from a Chapman–Enskog-like expansion.

A rigorous study of the sub-characteristic conditions for the present relaxation system is arduous, because the PDE system, $\partial_t \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{A} \partial_x \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}$, is conditionally hyperbolic and also because the analytical complexity of \mathbf{A} in the equilibrium system dramatically increases with N . Adopting a pragmatic numerical approach, we studied the simple cases with three layers and five layers. The analytical form of \mathbf{A} in the equilibrium system was obtained with the help of the computer algebra system (CAS), Maxima, while the one in the relaxation system is given by Eqs. (67)–(70), assuming that the transport velocities, u_i^* , are equal to the layers’ velocities. The eigenvalues sets of both PDE systems were numerically calculated for a large number of random states in the following ranges: $10^{-4} \text{ m} \leq \bar{v}_i h_i \leq 0.5 \text{ m}$, $-50 \text{ m/s} \leq \bar{v}_i u_{x,i} h_i / \bar{v}_i h_i \leq 50 \text{ m/s}$ and $0^\circ \leq \zeta \leq 60^\circ$. For each of 3- and 5-layers cases, 10^5 determinations of the reduced variables, $\mathbf{q}^* = (\{\bar{v}_i h_i, \bar{v}_i u_{x,i} h_i\}_{i=1,\dots,N})$ were randomly generated, while the equilibrium values of \bar{v}_i were subsequently calculated by Eqs. (52)–(56), with the parameters $d_g = 0.001 \text{ m}$, $\nu_{min} = 0.10$, $\nu_{max} = 0.64$ and $a' = 0.5$. First, we observed that the eigenvalues of the two systems are typically very close to each other in both their real and imaginary parts. For a direct comparison of the eigenvalues, the transport velocities are temporarily removed from the eigenvalues’ set of the relaxation system, and the $2N$ eigenvalues of the relaxation and equilibrium systems are sorted by their real part in ascending order, $\Re(\lambda_1) \leq \Re(\lambda_2) \dots \leq \Re(\lambda_{2N})$. We define the relative deviations of the real and imaginary parts for the generic i -th eigenvalue,

$$E_{\Re,i} = \frac{\Re(\lambda_{i,relax}) - \Re(\lambda_{i,equil})}{|\Re(\lambda_{i,relax})|}, \quad E_{\Im,i} = \frac{\Im(\lambda_{i,relax}) - \Im(\lambda_{i,equil})}{|\Re(\lambda_{i,relax})|}. \quad (A2)$$

For the 3-layer and 5-layer cases, respectively, 97.6% and 98.4% of the investigated states exhibit $|E_{\Re,i}| < 1\%$ with median values of 0.00046 and 0.00029. In addition, 98.2% and 98.4% of the non-hyperbolic states exhibit $|E_{\Im,i}| < 1\%$ with median values of 0.00015 and 0.00016, respectively. Since the extreme (barotropic) eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} are always real (e.g., Audusse, 2005), the sub-characteristic conditions, (A1), can be easily verified. Specifically, 99.2% and 99.3% of the investigated states, respectively for the 3-layer and 5-layer models, are found to fulfill (A1) (Fig. 10). Occasional violations of (A1) are numerically observed (Fig. 11) but the relative deviations are very small with maximum values equal to 0.0069 and 0.0041, for the 3-layer and 5-layer cases, respectively. Few extra calculations, performed with 500-digits precision and on a smaller dataset of 10^3 states, showed that the violations of (A1) slightly decrease in magnitude, suggesting that they could be caused by rounding errors.

To be able to check the sub-characteristic conditions for the internal waves, we restrained our investigation to the sole hyperbolic states. Considering all the $3N$ eigenvalues of the relaxation system sorted in ascending order, these further sub-characteristic conditions (Chen *et al.*, 1994) read as

$$\lambda_{i,relax} \leq \lambda_{i,equil} \leq \lambda_{i+3N-2N,relax}, \quad 1 < i < 2N. \quad (A3)$$

The inequalities (A3) are fulfilled in the vast majority of cases: i.e., 99.96% and 99.95%, respectively, for the 3-layer and 5-layer models. The rare violations of (A3) are again very small and exhibit a

FIG. 10. Comparisons of the minimum and maximum eigenvalues for the relaxation and equilibrium models (10^5 random states): (a) 3-layers and (b) 5-layers.

FIG. 11. Weak violations of the inequalities (A1) (double precision): (a) 3-layers (median value of $|E| = |\lambda_{relax} - \lambda_{equil}|/|\lambda_{relax}|$ equal to 2.6×10^{-6}), inset: calculations with 500-digits precision, median value 1.2×10^{-7} , (b) 5-layers (median value 4.4×10^{-6}), inset: calculations with 500-digits precision, median value 5.5×10^{-6} .

maximum overshoot (calculated as $|\lambda_{i,relax} - \lambda_{i,equil}|/|\lambda_{i,relax}|$ or $|\lambda_{i+3N-2N,relax} - \lambda_{i,equil}|/|\lambda_{i+3N-2N,relax}|$ equal to 0.028 and 0.0013 for the 3-layer and 5-layer models.

The above results, obtained on 3- and 5-layer models, clearly indicate that the stiff relaxation of \bar{v}_i is numerically stable without the need of additional time step constraints. This behavior is expected to hold also for $N > 5$, as corroborated by the numerical convergence of the simulations reported in Sec. V.

APPENDIX B: NUMERICAL SCHEME

The numerical integration of the PDE system (66) is briefed here. A uniform mesh Δx is employed, while the time step Δt is chosen to fulfill the conventional CFL condition. With reference to the generic time-point j and cell r , the numerical solution (here considered without \bar{v}_i for notation convenience) is denoted with \mathbf{Q}_r^j ,

while the intermediate solutions are denoted with $\mathbf{Q}_r^I, \mathbf{Q}_r^II$, etc. The following time-splitting approach (e.g., LeVeque, 2004) is used:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Stage I: } & \mathbf{q}(t=t^j) = \mathbf{Q}_r^j, \quad d\mathbf{q}/dt = \mathbf{s}_{res} \xrightarrow{\Delta t/2} \mathbf{Q}_r^I, \\
 \text{Stage II: } & \mathbf{q}(t=t^j) = \mathbf{Q}_r^I, \quad \partial_t \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{s}_{diff}(\mathbf{q}, \partial_x \mathbf{q}, \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}) \xrightarrow{\Delta t/2} \mathbf{Q}_r^{II}, \\
 \text{Stage III: } & \mathbf{q}(t=t^j) = \mathbf{Q}_r^{II}, \quad \partial_t \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{A} \partial_x \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{s}_{topo} \xrightarrow{\Delta t} \mathbf{Q}_r^{III}, \\
 \text{Stage IV: } & \mathbf{q}(t=t^j) = \mathbf{Q}_r^{III}, \quad \partial_t \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{s}_{diff}(\mathbf{q}, \partial_x \mathbf{q}, \partial_{xx} \mathbf{q}) \xrightarrow{\Delta t/2} \mathbf{Q}_r^{IV}, \\
 \text{Stage V: } & \mathbf{q}(t=t^j) = \mathbf{Q}_r^{IV}, \quad d\mathbf{q}/dt = \mathbf{s}_{res} \xrightarrow{\Delta t/2} \mathbf{Q}_r^{j+1}, \\
 \text{Stage VI: } & (\bar{v}_i)_r^{j+1} = (\bar{v}_{i,EOS})_r^{j+1}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{B1}$$

In the first five stages, \bar{v}_i is treated explicitly. In Stages I and V, accounting for the resistances \mathbf{s}_{res} , a two-stage scheme is used to

solve the ordinary differential equation (ODE) system. Specifically, we employed a semi-implicit Euler scheme (e.g., Sarno *et al.*, 2021b), where the quantities involved in the shear stresses, (65), are evaluated explicitly except for factor $\Delta_z u_x|_{i+1/2}$ that is treated implicitly. The solution of the predictor stage is then used to estimate the explicit quantities in the corrector stage. Although this ODE solver is formally first-order accurate, it is computationally efficient, as it only involves tri-diagonal linear systems instead of accurately solving $N \times N$ non-linear systems. Moreover, it has excellent stability properties, different e.g., from the trapezoidal and midpoint schemes, which were found to exhibit unstable behavior especially near the state of rest. The constant δ for the $\|\mathbf{D}\|$ regularization in (65) is set to 10^{-6}s^{-1} .

The diffusion-like term, \mathbf{s}_{diff} , considered in stages II and IV, is treated in an explicit way with the second-order derivatives being approximated by the central difference scheme, $(\partial_{xx}f)_r = (f_{r+1}^I - 2f_r^I + f_{r-1}^I)/\Delta x^2 + \mathcal{O}(\Delta x^2)$ and the non-linear terms by $(\partial_x f \partial_x g)_r = (f_{r+1}^I - f_{r-1}^I)(g_{r+1}^I - g_{r-1}^I)/\Delta x^2 + \mathcal{O}(\Delta x^2)$ (here written with reference to Stage II). To ensure the numerical stability of stages II and IV, a time-marching approach with $\Delta t_{multi-step,i} \leq \Delta t/2$ is required. For each layer, the following time constraint is considered:

$$\Delta t_{multi-step,i} \leq \frac{1}{4\psi} \frac{\Delta x^2}{\max_x(\max(\sqrt{p_{norm,i}}|q_{3i}/q_{3i-1}|, \sqrt{p_{norm,i}}))}, \quad (\text{B2})$$

where the maximum is evaluated over the entire spatial domain, and $\sqrt{p_{norm,i}}|q_{3i}/q_{3i-1}|$ and $\sqrt{p_{norm,i}}$ are obtained from the i th row of the diffusion matrix, \mathbf{H} (80), evaluated as a function of \mathbf{Q} (i.e., \mathbf{Q}^I with reference to Stage II). In (B2), $\Delta t_{multi-step,i}$ are chosen to be divisors of $\Delta t/2$, so that the solution for all layers can be straightforwardly updated at the end of the stage.

In Stage III, the advection term, $\mathbf{A}\partial_x \mathbf{q}$, and topographic terms, \mathbf{s}_{topo} , are treated by a finite volume scheme with the lateralized Harten–Lax–van Leer (LHLL) approximate Riemann solver (Fracarollo *et al.*, 2003), already employed for the two-layer model by Sarno *et al.* (2014, 2017). This scheme, which is path-conservative in the sense of Parés (2006), is an extension of the Harten–Lax–van Leer (HLL) scheme (Harten *et al.*, 1983), where the non-conservative terms are treated in a lateralized fashion. High resolution in space is achieved thanks to a MUSCL predictor-corrector treatment (van Leer, 1977), based on a minmod-limited linear reconstruction (for details see Fracarollo *et al.*, 2003). The Riemann problems between wet and dry cells are treated by adding a small thickness to each layer of 10^{-6}m . The following formulas, tested on a large number of numerical solutions, are used in the LHLL scheme as lower and upper bounds of the eigenvalues set [cf. Eqs. (67)–(70)]:

$$S_R = \min\left(0, \min(u_i) - \sqrt{g_z \sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{v}_i h_i) / \min(\bar{v}_i)}\right), \quad (\text{B3})$$

$$S_L = \max\left(0, \max(u_i) + \sqrt{g_z \sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{v}_i h_i) / \min(\bar{v}_i)}\right).$$

It is worth underlining that the LHLL solver only uses these bounds of the eigenvalues set and, hence, is able to advance the solution in

time even if some eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} are complex. The global bound of the eigenvalue set,

$$\max(|\lambda|) \leq \max_x \left(\max|u_i| + \sqrt{g_z \sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{v}_i h_i) / \min \bar{v}_i} \right), \quad (\text{B4})$$

is used to ensure the fulfillment of the CFL condition. The volume fractions, $(\bar{v}_i)_r^{j+1}$, are updated in Stage VI by stiff relaxation, i.e., using the EOS, Eq. (56), as a function of the numerical solution \mathbf{Q}_r^{j+1} .

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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